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Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
Main authors:		
Roskilde University	Magnus Paulsen Hansen	mapaha@ruc.dk
Roskilde University	Sabina Pultz	spultz@ruc.dk
Contributing authors		
University of Ljubljana	Tjaša Redek	tjasa.redek@ef.uni-lj.si
University of Ljubljana	Marko Pahor	marko.pahor@ef.uni-lj.si
University of Ljubljana	Mojca Svetek	
Employment Services of Slovenia	Martina Rameša	martina.ramesa@ess.gov.si

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Abstract

The user context document describes the environment around unemployment services and outlines the considerations for social requirements when developing the platform in Slovenia. Based on document studies, statistics and interviews with counsellors and unemployed persons at the pilot deployment sites we aim to capture the user environment. Although, Slovenia has had its own unique path towards activation which is shaped by the past socialist era as a republic in Yugoslavia and subsequent transition, it also shares several characteristics and challenges with most other EU member states. Thus, the report points to the issues related to profiling and the Hecat tool that are distinctly Slovenian and those that will be relevant in other countries.

Statement of originality

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1 Introduction

1.1 Contribution to the Hecat project

This report is the last deliverable of work package 1 in the Hecat Horizon 2020 project. The aim of this deliverable is to describe the ‘user context’ of the Hecat platform. While the long-term goal of the platform is to be relevant and useful across the European countries, it is in Slovenia that the platform is developed and piloted. Hence, the report describes the environment around unemployment services and outlines the considerations for social requirements when developing the platform in Slovenia. We do this with a two-fold aim. First, to provide the necessary insights to the context in which the platform is going to be piloted. Second, to understand the Slovenian context as a test case for future platforms in other European countries. In other words, the report makes it possible to assess in what ways the Slovenian context is distinct or generalizable to other countries.

As stated in the Grant agreement, being part of work package 1, entails that this user context document is underpinning a ‘sociologically-led user design’ and the ethos of working **with** rather than **on** the unemployed. This means that rather than paying attention to technical and short-term functional needs of the public employment services (PES), our perspective takes departure in the ‘experience of unemployment’ from the perspective, first, of the unemployed, and second, of the counsellors working at the ‘street-level’ of public employment services. Because the work has been constrained by the COVID-19 pandemic, the report is based on both online interviews, however ethnographic fieldwork was also carried out at the two piloting sites in Slovenia in the cities of Ptuj and Ljubljana. This report is thus the first initial step towards giving the unemployed a ‘voice in the algorithm’.

The report builds on the ‘D1.4 User vision statement’ that pointed to the importance of ‘the lived experiences of the unemployed’, the public policies and institutional actions that target the unemployed and influence their experiences, i.e. ‘the government of the experiences of the unemployed’; the situations of the unemployed in the labour market and with regard to employment that influence the attributed and experienced meanings of unemployment, i.e. the inequalities within unemployment’ (Demazière and Delpierre, 2020). It also builds on the insights from ‘D1.3 Report on ethical, social, theological, technical review of 1st generation PES algorithms and database’ that points to how ‘first generation algorithms focus on addressing PES process needs, particularly preventing PES case worker service from being overwhelmed’ and thus argues that ‘as such the algorithms do not directly work on the core PES challenge of supporting long-term unemployment (LTU), rather they work on an unrelated symptom of high rates of general unemployment which cyclically arise in certain countries.’ (Griffin et al. 2021, p. 41).

Both deliverables also point to the potential tension between the ethos of working **with** the unemployed and the general trend towards active labour market policies (ALMP) and activation across Europe. While these policies have accentuated the need for reintegrating the unemployed in the labour market, they have also introduced instruments governing the

behaviour of the unemployed, that is systems of control, conditionality, and sanctions, that in essence work **on** the unemployed. Thus, we have paid special attention to the historical and political role of the ‘active turn’ in Slovenia and how it plays out in the local employment offices as well as how it is experienced by the unemployed. Since the algorithm of the Hecat platform inevitably will be visualizing, not only the labour market, but also the unemployed, we also explore the role of existing categorization and profiling tools.

However, as mentioned above, the experience of unemployment is not only related to the encounters with PES, but also with the labour market, through past experiences and the versatile activities of job search. Thus, we explore how the dynamics of the labour market affect the experience of unemployment as well as the work carried out in the PES. This will provide important insights to what needs of the unemployed the Hecat platform may satisfy as well as the limitations and challenges that an algorithm faces in visualizing a labour market in which so many dynamics are invisible to or skewed in available statistical data.

1.2 Structure of the report

The report is structured as follows. In the following sections of **chapter 1**, we briefly outline our theoretical approach and the methods and research design of the study. The remaining of the report is composed of three parts. **Part I** aims to provide readers with the historical, political and institutional context of the PES in Slovenia. In **chapter 2** we provide a brief history of labour market policies in Slovenia in which we point to the importance of Slovenia’s distinct socialist past as being part of Yugoslavia making the transition of Slovenia in the 1990s unlike most other East and Central European countries. It then describes the introduction of active labour market policies beginning in the 1990s while, finally addressing changes since the financial crisis, that like so many other countries, had substantial effect from which Slovenia had only recovered from as the COVID-19 pandemic again changes things substantially. In **chapter 3** we describe the governance of PES in Slovenia, both the organization and how the local PES are held to account, for instance through the performance measurement of implementation and service delivery.

In **part 2** we zoom in on the activities and practices in the local PES. In **chapter 4** we describe the benefit systems and rights of the unemployed, the variety of activation measures offered, and the obligations and conditionality of the unemployed, including the use of sanctioning. **Chapter 5** describes the counselling practices and how these are experienced by the unemployed. We zoom in on the role of profiling and categorization. In the final **part III** we explore the characteristics of the labour market and the role of job-seeking. **Chapter 6** describes the unemployed, in numbers and figures and through their own experiences. In chapter 7 and 8 we address two dynamics in the Slovenian labour – the role and prevalence of precarious work in **chapter 7** and the role of informality as informal work and kinship in **chapter 8**. In **chapter 9** we briefly outline reflections on the HECAT platform and in **chapter 10** we assess the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic on the labour market in Slovenia. In **chapter 11** we end the report with a brief conclusion summarizing our findings. Parts of the report is co-written with the University of Ljubljana team and the

ESS team. In these cases, authors are listed below the title of the chapter or subchapter. Each chapter ends with emphasizing the most important key takeaways.

1.3 Theoretical approach

The aim of the analysis is to explore the Slovenian unemployment experience and focusing on how they experience PES, the labour market as well as their possibilities here. To explore the unemployment experience, we are inspired by the theoretical framework from governmentality studies (Foucault, 2008) that aims at exploring the various ways people are governed in societies involving both the ways people are governed through official laws, rules and policies, how these are put into practice in everyday life as well as how people govern themselves through understandings (Rose, 1996). Within unemployment studies, governmentality studies have received quite a lot of attention and studies along these lines have documented the construction of the active jobseeker because of the introduction of the activation paradigm, described more elaborately later on (Boland and Griffin, 2015; Dean, 1995; Pultz, 2017; Walters, 2000).

Also, scholars from within the field of street-level bureaucracy (SLB) have advocated that it is necessary to consider how policies are administered by the frontline personnel who meet citizens and translate the policies into practices in various ways (Lipsky, 2010). Policies are not only implemented, rather, the policies emerge and are constituted through the ways they are translated and used in practice in the meeting between the frontline servant and the citizen, in this case the unemployed person (Berkel et al., 2017; Brodtkin and Marston, 2013; Hupe et al., 2016). Only analysing changes at policy level does not necessarily give an accurate picture of the everyday practices. Lipsky, who coined the term and paved the way for this line of work, defined SLB as follows: “Public service workers who interact directly with citizens in the course of their jobs, and who have substantial discretion in the execution of their work” (Lipsky 2010, p. 3). In a Slovenian context, the SLB stands out as particularly important as counsellors working with unemployed people have large amount of discretion which we will elaborate below. To explore the “missing middle” in policy analysis (Brodtkin, 2013, Caswell, 2019), we therefore include qualitative analysis of the meeting between the counsellors and the unemployed people from both sides of the table.

To access and gain deep understanding of the unemployment experience, we shed light on technologies of power and technologies of the self. First, technologies of power involve the various ways that unemployed people are governed in the Slovenian PES, both in terms of an analysis of the policy and governance structure, largely informed by a document analysis, and in terms of exploring how laws and policies and how are put into practice in the daily interactions at PES. Here, we rely on field observations, qualitative interviews with PES counsellors and unemployed people, as well as focus groups conducted with counsellors. Secondly, we explore technologies of the self, which refer to how people conduct themselves and their everyday life more broadly. To do so, we rely mainly on the in-depth interviews with the unemployed people.

1.4 Methods

Exploring the unemployment experience in the context of Slovenian PES, we have gathered data based on following methods:

- Interviews with job counsellors (online and on-site) – recorded, transcribed and coded.¹
- Interviews with unemployed persons (online and on-site) – recorded, transcribed and coded.²
- Focus groups with job counsellors – recorded, transcribed and coded.³
- Observations, e.g., of sites, interviews between counsellors and unemployed and of workshops at the local PES. Field-notes and images.
- Additional sources: policy documents, statistics and surveys carried out in Slovenia, for instance by ESS and comparative statistics and analyses from OECD and the EU, existing qualitative and quantitative studies.

The interview participants range both in terms of education, age, socioeconomic status as well as between receiving no money, unemployment benefit and social welfare. In total we conducted 29 interviews, divided into 20 interviews with unemployed; 5 were online and held at various times between summer 2020 through September 2020, while the rest was equally distributed between interviews with unemployed in Ptuj and Ljubljana in connection with our field work in September 2020. Most of our interviews were conducted in English, but with the possibility of having a translator. Three interviews were done in Slovenian with a Slovenian interviewer from the University of Ljubljana. We conducted 8 online interviews with counsellors from both Ptuj and Ljubljana, and in addition we did one focus group-interview with 4-5 counsellors in both Ptuj and Ljubljana in September 2020. We have selected interview participants in order to explore the range of heterogeneity that characterize Slovenian citizens registered at PES (see Table 1 for sample characteristics)⁴ We have recruited interview participants through the ESS from whom we received contact information. Even though interview participants were granted anonymity, this sampling strategy constitutes a potential bias in the data as it might be difficult for participants to be open and honest about their experiences (and vent critique in terms of the PES) as they might expect that their answers will be somehow available for ESS. Further, the ESS may have an interest in filtering participants according to their own interest, which also constitutes a potential bias.

¹ Interview protocol is appendix 1.1.

² Interview protocol is appendix 1.2

³ Interview protocol is appendix 1.3

⁴ Interviews were carried out by Sabina Pultz, Maggie Müller and Magnus Paulsen Hansen from the Roskilde University team. The three interviews in Slovenian were carried out by Marko Pahor and Tjasa Redek with from the University of Ljubljana team.

Table 1 Sample characteristics

Interview characteristics	samples	Unemployed	Counsellors
Interview total		19	8 + 2
Online		5	8
On sight		7 in Ptuj 7 in Ljubljana	1 focus group in both Ptuj and Ljubljana
Gender		11 Women 8 Men	7 Women 2 Men
Education:		3 w. no education 3 w. lower education 11 w. higher education 1 student 1 unknown	-
Age		20-30: 5 participants 30-40: 5 participants 40-50: 2 participants 50-60: 6 participants Unknown: 1 participant	-

The interviews were based on a protocol designed to elicit information about the interview participants' situation and personal circumstances, how they experience being unemployed as well as how they experience the unemployment system and their counsellor. For the use of this report, we have anonymized names. Demazière & Delpierre (2020) highlight multiple points of interest from the literature on unemployment and we are inspired by these in the analysis such as; lived experience of being unemployed covering everyday life as unemployed, social relations, job search, meaningful activities, as well as issues of inequality in the labour market. Hence, we have asked questions about the Slovenian labour market and about their job search, including information about what kind of jobs they seek, how mobile and flexible they are (in terms of profession, geography and salary) and we have asked them about their notions of what a good job entails from their vantage point.

Each interview lasted between 30 minutes to one hour. The interview participants were notified that they could withdraw from the study at any given moment, and that the data would be anonymized.

To provide transparency in the work, we describe the analytical process in more detail. Initially we read through the transcripts several times and based on that we developed a protocol for coding categories consisting of relatively descriptive categories such as assessment of system, client – counsellor interactions, everyday life and job search. The

research team coded the entire material. We have structured the analysis by first exploring how the Slovenian unemployed people experience the PES, including how they experience making the individual plan, how they experience the relationship to the counsellor and the obligations they have. Following that we explore how the unemployed people experience their job search. This includes their reflections about the Slovenian labour market, including the importance of having networks and what the various perceptions about what a good job entail. Finally, we explore what they think of the HECAT platform.

1.5 Acknowledgements

This report would not have been possible without the help and dedication of several people. First, we are indebted to our brilliant research assistant Maggie Müller who has contributed to the making of this report from carrying out field work, transcription and coding to analysing and editing. Second, we would like to thank the University of Ljubljana team – Marko Pahor, Mojca Svetek, and Tjaša Redek for providing valuable input to part I and for helping out with interviewing in Ljubljana and Ptuj. Third, we would like to thank Martina Rameša from ESS for helping us with, well everything, from providing data and organizing the field work. Marko Pahor, Mojca Svetek, Tjaša Redek and Martina Rameša have also co-authored parts of the report: chapters 3 and 4 and section 5.1, 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4.

In general, we would like to thank the ESS for being so supportive and opening their doors without conditions for this inquiry. We are extremely grateful to Tjaša Fužir at the Ljubljana office and Lea Štiberc at the Ptuj office for helping with recruitment and organizing visits. Finally, we would like to thank all the counsellors and unemployed at the regional employment offices in Ljubljana and Ptuj for participating in this study. Despite the invaluable help from ‘locals’, most of this report is written by a team of ‘foreigners’. Sometimes the foreigner’s perspective enables to see things that are taken for granted to locals, sometimes it works the opposite way, at worst, leading to misinterpretations. Both scenarios could indeed apply to this report, although we have done our best to avoid the latter.

Part I

The history, policies, and governance of unemployment in Slovenia

2 A brief history of labour market policies in Slovenia

2.1 *The transition*

In 1991, Slovenia declared independence from Yugoslavia initiating a peaceful transition to become a capitalist democracy while the rest of the former Yugoslavian republics went into consecutive bloody wars ending with the insurgency in Macedonia in 2001 (Calic, 2019). Although the transition from a socialist to a capitalist economy led to radical changes of the functioning and governance of the labour market, it is also described as a ‘soft transition’ in which much of the institutional legacy from the socialist era was somehow moulded rather than simply abandoned in the transition, enabling the country to absorb economic shocks (Ignjatović et al., 2002) and avoid the kind of neoliberal ‘shock therapy’ and extensive privatisation preached and practiced in many other post-socialist countries at the time (Kolarič et al., 2011).

Part of the explanation to this transition lies in the distinct economic model often labelled ‘market socialism’ in the Socialist Federative Republic of Yugoslavia differed from most other socialist Central and East-European countries’ planned economies. Already since the mid-1960s elements of a market economy was introduced such as liberalizing trade and trade increasingly oriented towards foreign countries in the West, while the system of ‘self-management’ at the level of enterprises granted workers substantial means to voice and exit through ‘work councils’ and strikes (Bacevic, 2014; Stanojević, 2000). This legacy of self-management was transformed into a distinct variety of neo-corporatism thoroughly including labour in political decision-making and supported by a stable centre-left coalition of government lasting until the EU accession in 2004 (Bohle and Greskovits, 2007; Crowley and Stanojević, 2011).

The market economy elements meant that, even though there was a constitutional right to work, it was not realized in practice (Dropnic and Rus, 1995: 94). Rather, and contrary to most Central and East European countries, unemployment in Yugoslavia was a permanent characteristic of the labour market (Dropnic and Rus, 1995). For these reasons, and tied to the region’s Austro-Hungarian past, a Bismarckian-style insurance scheme for unemployment was introduced in Slovenia in the mid 1970s long before the transition (Wright et al., 2003). Despite being placed in a socialist economic system, the ‘silent partnership between the working class and the ruling Communist party nomenclature’ in which political legitimacy was traded for assuring lifelong employment and social protection was compatible with Bismarckian ideas of contributory and equity principles (Kolarič et al., 2011). Thus, it is of no surprise that comparative welfare scholars have argued that Slovenia (along with other Central Eastern post-communist welfare states) have returned to their pre-socialist historical roots and thus sharing major traits with the Continental welfare regimes (Aspalter, Jinsoo, & Sojeung, 2009; cf. Esping-Andersen, 1990; Fenger, 2007). The Slovenian version of ‘competitive neo-corporatism’ evolved into a complex system of collective bargaining at micro and sectoral levels, and political exchanges with unions at the macro-level of the social system in which some rationalization

of production as well as Europeanization of policies were traded in exchange for employment and income stability (Stanojević, 2014: 104).

The existence of a labour market with some degree of supply and demand dynamics in the socialist period was also underpinned by a network of public employment services as well as a few active labour market programmes (OECD, 1997). However, the guaranteed right to life-long employment, meant that the system only had to deal with relatively rare instances of those marginal to the labour market, the hard-to-place unemployed and people incapable of work (Ignjatović et al., 2002). There are two other institutions that have proven to be mouldable to contemporary aims of labour market governance. The first is the aim since the 1970s of aligning educational programmes, through ‘profiles’ designed to fit specific types of jobs, with the needs of labour market. These policies are thus not so far from the current EU agenda of life-long learning and employability although the latter tends to emphasize flexibility and individuals rather than classes (Bacevic, 2014). The second is the extensive network of preschools and scheme of parental rights established in the 1970s, that is crucial to explain why Slovenia is one of the most notable countries in the EU of an ‘adult worker model’ in which both men and women participate in full-time paid work (Hrženjak, 2017: 214).

It was not simply the absence of war that made Slovenia’s transition smoother than the rest of former Yugoslav countries. Even in the socialist era, Slovenia was the region with by far the lowest unemployment rate in Yugoslavia – around 3 percent, in practice close to full employment, in the 1980s while the rate for the whole of the country was around 15 percent. (Dropnic and Rus, 1995). According to Wright et al., of all the Central and East European countries, Slovenia was, and perhaps still is, distinct, not only because of its small size, but ‘due to its affluence and outward-looking stance’ (Wright et al., 2003: 4).⁵

2.2 The active turn in Slovenia

Even though the transition was relatively smooth, the years around the declaration of independence were, like most other Central and Eastern European countries at the time, characterized by a steep rise in unemployment increasing by five times from 89 to 94, caused by decreasing employment in particular in manufacturing, construction and trade (Dropnic & Rus, 1995). Even though the effects were mitigated by ‘soft lay-off practices’ (retirement and deteriorated dependency ratios) (Ministrstvo za delo, družino, socialne zadeve in enake možnosti, 2016) the rising unemployment rates put financial pressure on the systems of social security and unemployment insurance while the privileges and access to unemployment benefits were increasingly problematized as inhibiting unemployed from accessing the labour market (Ignjatović et al., 2002). This led to the gradual change in the understanding of the unemployed as somehow responsible for his or her situation and to a reorientation of policies towards questions of availability to work, toughening sanctions and,

⁵ We return to this matter in part III.

inspired by the British model, adopting individual action plans (Ignjatović et al., 2002; Wright et al., 2003).

In this way, Slovenia committed itself to the ‘active turn’ (Bonoli, 2010; Hansen, 2019) of reforming labour market policies at the same time as the first movers elsewhere in Europe such as the UK, Denmark and the Netherlands. Thus, rights (for instance to unemployment insurance) have been connected to various responsibilities or obligations, while employment programmes have reoriented from demand-side (e.g. focus on employers and jobs creation) to the supply side (the unemployed) (Ignjatović et al., 2002). This development seems to be closely related to the strong support for preparing for accession to the EU in the 1990s in which the pull of Europeanization and the idea of the ‘European social model’ was a major force (Stanojević, 2000). It was law from 1998 that marked the turn towards activation, tying rights closely to obligations (Kolarič et al., 2011: 297).

Until 1998 the right to benefits was the primary right of the unemployed. The Law changed that, and the primary right of the unemployed was their inclusion into the active labour market programs to increase employability and to stimulate the unemployed to more actively search for work. Namely, the individual could maintain the right to benefits only if he/she actively searches for employment and there is no appropriate job for him/her. The benefits were limited to 12 months and were given for a period between 3-12 months depending on previous employment (insurance) length. The law also introduced special protection of the older workers. They were eligible for benefits for 18 months, conditional on age (50+) and total employment length (25 years minimum). If then after the 18 months pass, the person had less than 3 years to retirement, the ESS would pay retirement insurance and special benefits. The law also introduced subsidies for employers, that employ an unemployed person for at least 2 years (Zavod RS za zaposlovanje, 2020b).

While the turn towards activation was to some extent driven and informed by EU and OECD recommendations, Slovenia chose a distinct reform pattern mixing the active agenda with its historical institutional path. Wright et al. thus noted in the early 2000s that the commitment to ‘the value of egalitarianism (...) has survived, alongside meritocratic social protection, to shape the nature and extent of activation avoiding the jettisoning of strong social rights’ and promoting access to good quality jobs rather than work first at any cost (Wright et al., 2003).⁶ Others, however, see the reforms of the 1990s as the beginning of a ‘a continual gradual retrenchment of the system, where the maximum payments were decreased and period for receiving the benefit shortened’ (Hrast et al., 2020).

⁶ This diagnosis has many similarities with the diagnoses of the Danish reform path in the same period. For instance, some saw the Danish reforms in the 1990s as following the existing social democratic ‘path’ seeing the active labour market policy measures as add-on to existing welfare institutions (Torfing, 2001). In this way, Denmark had chosen a ‘human capital’ strategy as opposed to the ‘work first’ strategy most Anglo-Saxon countries had taken since the 1980s. The strategy entailed activation rather than coercive benefit and wage reductions; improving the skills and work experience of the unemployed rather than merely increasing their mobility, job-search efficiency and *quid pro quo*; and, finally, empowerment rather than control and punishment (Torfing, 1999: 17; Hansen and Leschke, 2022).

In 2004, the same year Slovenia joined the EU, the centre-left coalition lost government office to Janez Janša, leader of the conservative Slovenian Democratic Party. Janša pursued a neoliberal reform agenda but was largely unsuccessful in his attempts, in particular due to public opinion strong opposition from labour unions (Hrast Filipovič and Raka, 2017) that were being excluded from the policy-making process (Stanojević, 2014). For instance, the administrative role of the social partners within the Employment Service was reduced, allegedly to accommodate the European Employment Strategy, as the board did not include all Ministries responsible for its implementation (Guardiancich, 2011). However, some reforms were carried through. In 2006 a reform further strengthened conditionality by introducing financial sanctioning (Kolarič et al., 2011: 297).⁷ The reform also abolished the unemployment assistance scheme for unemployed people in need, after the expiry of their earnings-based unemployment benefit, thus, making social assistance the only alternative (Ibid.).

2.3 Post Financial crisis

The economic repercussions of the financial crisis in 2008, were substantial in Slovenia leading to a fall in GDP by 8 percent in 2009, a rise in the budget deficit from 1.8 percent of GDP in 2008 to 5.8 percent in 2009 (Stanojević, 2014: 107), and a steep increase in unemployment rate peaking in 2014 at around 10 percent (see figure 1) followed by a rather slow recovery, partly due to low domestic demand (Cristescu et al., 2015). In climate of unstable governments, the subsequent years (Hrast Filipovič and Raka, 2017), several reforms, touching the labour market regulation and social policy, were aiming to cut costs and restore financial sustainability (Hrast et al., 2020: 698). Whereas social protection spending has remained at the same level from 2000 to 2015 (around 24 % of GDP), unemployment benefit expenditure has decreased gradually from 4.15 % in 2000 to 2.69 % in 2015, while social exclusion expenditure has increased from 1.6% to 3.11 % in the same period (Hrast et al., 2020: 696).

⁷ We elaborate further on the rules of conditionality and practices of sanctioning in section 4.1 ‘Obligations and sanctions’.

Figure 1: Economic growth (%) (SI-GDP and EU-GDP) and ILO unemployment rate (%) (SI-UN and EU-UN) in Slovenia and in the EU (Pahor et al., 2020)

Source: Data derived from World Bank, 2020

However, reforms in the aftermath of the financial crisis should not simply be labelled as neoliberal austerity and retrenchment. Rather they were a composite mix of policies aiming to induce more flexibility into the labour market, cut costs, and provide protection for those hit by the ‘dualization’ (Emmenegger et al., 2012) dynamics of the labour market (Bembič and Stanojević, 2016).⁸ Policies, thus included temporary subsidies of full-time work for part-time workers, increasing protection for more vulnerable workers, raising the minimum wage, softening the eligibility criteria for those with a more irregular employment record, increasing the level of unemployment benefit, and raising contributions from employees and employers for fixed term contracts to stimulate permanent contracts (Hrast et al., 2020: 699). Also, active labour market policies and social investment policies were implemented, but with limited resources (Ibid.; see also section 1.4). The reforms were loosely inspired by the concept of flexicurity – a concept used to describe first the Dutch and later the Danish labour market regulation and policies (see Madsen, 2002; Wilthagen and Tros, 2004).

While the Danish flexicurity model of generous unemployment benefits and extensive use of active labour market policies were unrealistic due to the Slovenian quasi-Continental model, lack of trust between social partners, and budget constraints (Kajzer, 2007) reforms in 2010 and 2013 focused on labour market regulation. In 2010 the Labour market Regulation Act (Zakon o Urejanju Trga Dela (ZUTD), 2010) introduced several important

⁸ We return to the issue of dualization in Chapter 7.

steps towards on the one hand addressing rigidity in the labour market, while on the other hand also correcting for some of the existing problems such as lowering the impact of the unemployment trap and lowering administrative barriers in the labour market (primarily for the employers).

The 2013 Employment Relationship Act (ERA) reduced the difference in costs between employing a worker under a fixed-term and a permanent contract by introducing severance pay, increasing the unemployment insurance contribution rate, and restricting leeway for contract extensions for fixed-term workers while it reduced the level of severance pay and the advance notice period and significantly simplified procedures for the dismissal of permanent workers (Vodopivec, 2019). The attempt to improve conditions for vulnerable workers was most evident in raising the national minimum wage and softening the eligibility criteria for receiving unemployment benefits making those in more irregular, flexible jobs, eligible (Hrast Filipovič and Raka, 2017).⁹ The reform was introduced in the aftermath of a massive civil society movement, particularly involving young educated, unemployed people, who carried out a series of mass protests against the government and the entire political elite (Stanojević, 2014: 108). However, many of these positive developments of the reform were reversed by neoliberal austerity measures that again reduced the unemployment benefit level and shortened benefit durations (Hrast Filipovič and Raka, 2017).

An important change in the system of social assistance was the introduction of conditionality and social investment granting recipients of social assistance a financial bonus if they are deemed active (are employed, participating in active labour market policy or psychosocial rehabilitation programmes or performing voluntary work) (Hrast et al., 2020: 705). In 2012 stricter eligibility criteria were introduced to the social assistance scheme replacing universal rights with extensive means-testing (Hrast Filipovič and Raka, 2017: 122).

To conclude, whereas Slovenia, in a comparative perspective still has a more universal and egalitarian approach to social and labour market policies it has also been shaped by ideas of both conditionality and work first as well as social investment and social protection. The approach ‘partly follows a social investment approach that emphasizes the relevance of labour market inclusion, but it can also partly be seen as a consequence of a more neoliberal agenda, with an emphasis on labour market participation (Hrast et al., 2020: 708). This hybrid (Aurich, 2008) or composite (Hansen, 2019) nature of labour market policies after the ‘active turn’ is not unique to Slovenia, but characteristic of most OECD countries. They all contain de-commodifying as well as re-commodifying elements and coercive as well as enabling elements, but each with a distinct blend (Aurich, 2011; see also Demazière and Delpierre, 2020: 20). Yet it seems that the ‘active turn’ has not had as radical effects as in many other countries. As illustrated above, this can, at least partially, be explained by Slovenia’s distinct historical legacy. However, in the following we zoom in on other factors that influence the actual governing of unemployment at the local public employment offices

⁹ In the early 1990s, minimum wages were determined through collective agreements, which was replaced by the statutory minimum wage (40% of the average gross wage) in 1995 (Guardiancich, 2011).

(PES), that is the public governance of unemployment policies and the socio-economic indicators of the labour market and the unemployed.

Key take-aways

The Slovenian labour market policies are placed in a tension between historical institutional roots resembling the Continental welfare model and the Bismarckian unemployment insurance system, long-standing values of egalitarianism and social rights deriving from the socialist era, and a reform trend, since the 1990s towards of active labour market polices aiming to reintegrate the unemployed as soon as possible to the labour market by strengthening responsibility and obligations as well as increasing the human capital of the unemployed. The employment system is thus a hybrid with elements of both classic de-commodifying welfare and workfare elements of both work first and social investment.

3 Governance structure of employment policies

By Marko Pahor, Martina Rameša, Tjaša Redek, Mojca Svetek, and Magnus Paulsen Hansen

Several studies have pointed to how the ‘active turn’ has implications not for the **services** that are offered to unemployed persons but also the **governance** structures surrounding the activation schemes (Borghgi and van Berkel, 2007; Lødemel and Moreira, 2014; van Berkel, 2016; van Berkel et al., 2011). Scholars find a variety of public governance mixes (Borghgi and van Berkel, 2007; Brodtkin and Marston, 2013; Considine et al., 2015; Eydoux and Béraud, 2011; Heidenreich and Rice, 2016; Lødemel and Moreira, 2014), but some general trends seem to characterize the governance reforms relating to activation and employment policies: The displacement of the logic of services from entitlement to compensation benefits to rights *and* obligations of the unemployed to be active and re-integrate into the labour market, which is also the trend in Slovenia, arguably creates a need for a ‘second wave’ of governance reforms (Larsen, 2013), aiming to monitor the performance of the activation carried out by front-line workers in the local agencies. While **the first wave** was concerned with the activation of the unemployed, **the second wave** is concerned with the activation of the organisation responsible for delivering benefits and imposing requirements, as well as the activation of the frontline workers delivering the services. It is in this light we turn our focus towards the organizational and governance structures in Slovenia.

3.1 The organization of Employment Service of Slovenia (ESS)

The key institution from the perspective of implementing policies in the labour market is the Employment Service of Slovenia (ESS) which is organized in three organizational levels – the central office, 12 regional offices, with local labour offices (See Figure 2) (Redek, et al., 2020). ESS is an independent legal entity with public institute status operating uniformly across the whole of Slovenia (Zavod RS za zaposlovanje, 2020d). Under the Statute, the central ESS administrative bodies are: [OB] The ESS Administrative Board has 13 members, as follows: 6 Slovenian government representatives, 3 national employers’ representatives, 3 national trade union representatives and 1 representative of the ESS Works Council (Zavod RS za zaposlovanje, 2020d).

Figure 2: Organizational structure of Employment Service of Slovenia

Source: Zavod RS za zaposlovanje, 2020c in Redek et al., 2020.

The Employment service of Slovenia is run by the general manager and the ESS council. The ESS council consists of 13 members, organized in the same way as the ESS Administrative Board. The central office and the leadership are responsible for preparing the methodologies for a unified implementation of all procedure that are in the scope of the ESS. Besides that, the central office and leadership are also responsible for providing the support from the perspective of IT, analytics, legal, HR, financial, accounting and organizational support (Redek, et al., 2020, Zavod RS za zaposlovanje, 2020d).

The 12 regional offices are responsible for the implementation of tasks related to the field of work of the ESS, they also monitor the labour market trends at local level, support the local offices and cooperate at local level with employers and ESS sub-contractors. The local offices are responsible for the direct link between the ESS and the clients and for executing the policies of ESS (employment counselling, providing insurance for unemployment, implementing active employment policy programmes, and career guidance for young people and adults) (Zavod RS za zaposlovanje, 2020d). Since the central office is responsible of setting up the strategy of work and prescribe the procedures of work with unemployed persons, the local offices have limited ability to adjust these to local needs although they do differ depending on the needs of the local job seekers and even more on the actual size of the PES offices.

Figure 3: Employment Service of Slovenia (ESS) regional offices

Source: Data derived from Zavod RS za zaposlovanje, 2020a in Redek et al., 2020.

Entrance, Regional office Ljubljana

Entrance, Regional office Ptuj

3.2 Financing PES

Funds for the operation and implementation of the EES programs are provided on the basis of a contract between the Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities and the ESS. Sources of financing for cash benefits and other transfers to the unemployed are provided directly from the budget of the Republic of Slovenia, where funds are also collected from the contributions of employees and employers from paid salaries. The unemployment insurance benefit is financed (partly) out of the compulsory contributions paid by employees (0.14 percent of insured persons' gross wage) and their employers (0.06 percent of the gross wage) but the social contributions covers only some 18.9 percent of the expenditure related to payment of unemployment cash benefits. The rest is covered by the state from the national budget (Kolarič, Kopač and Mrak, 2011).

In 2018, ESS used EUR 265,8 mil for all purposes, of which EUR 237 mil was financed from the integral government budget within the budget items of the Ministry of labour and

EUR 22 mil from ESF funds. Of the various projects, most of which are also financed from ESF funds, EUR 6,2 mil were mainly intended for investment in the development of the ESS' work. EUR 555,421 was obtained from commercial activity and other sources (Zavod RS za zaposlovanje 2019 from Redek et al. 2020).

3.3 Performance and accountability

ESS employs a bottom-up approach in performance dialogue. Annual targets are set, where regional offices estimate the inflows and outflows and stock of unemployed, central office prepares key targets and discusses them with the regional office, which afterwards sets an action plan aimed at reaching the key performance indicators (KPI). KPIs are monitored monthly at national, regional and local offices level and cover all the key areas of ESS work. For 2020, those are: decrease in number of LTU, quick activation of the unemployed, increase efficiency of job referrals, retain the efficiency of ALMP and strengthen the digital cooperation with costumers (ESS business plan 2020).

The performance dialogue at **local office level** consists of local office managers monitoring reaching the targets goals set in ESS business plan and regional office action plan, as well as monitoring individual employment counsellors (data for all counsellors are prepared by Central office). Results are shared among the staff monthly. At the **regional level** the regional office management monitors the target reaching trough monthly performance meetings where results of monitoring are presented, good practices shared and results are discussed and, where needed, corrective actions are proposed. On the **national level** monthly reporting at the ESS management board meeting among management and regional office directors, presentation of results, feedback, identification of good practices for internal knowledge transfer, agreement on corrective actions for improvement. On the European level Employment Service is evaluated and monitored within benchmarking assessment.

Additional aspects of internal monitoring are monitoring quality of counselling work, and an analysis of overall measure of performance in all regional offices, which is performed by the Analytics department at the Central office. Measure of performance includes dimensions of successful employment of the vulnerable groups, job referrals, and employments after enrolment in ALMP programmes and user survey satisfaction among unemployed and employers.

The central office is responsible of setting up the strategy of work and prescribe the procedures of work with unemployed persons, whereas the local PES and individual advisors are responsible of the implementation of the doctrine and procedures. Once these are set, local offices have limited ability to adjust these to local needs. The operations of the local PES differ a bit depending on the needs of the local job seekers and even more on the actual size of a PES office, but they always stick to the doctrine and procedures. However, it should be noted that local offices consult regional and central in preparation of suggestions.

These are then reported to ESS central offices and are also reflected in the decisions on ALMP at national (ministry) level.

To conclude, what we see in Slovenia is a rather ‘soft’ second wave of governance. Similar to many other countries this ‘second wave’ of reforms have come with a variety of instruments from the palette of New Public Management, such as contracting out, performance measurement, benchmarking, and pay-for-performance systems (Larsen, 2013; van Berkel, 2016), creating an additional layer of accountability, involving not only local providers of activation but also more central agencies monitoring their performance. The effects of such reforms depend on the concrete design of the performance management systems as well as the local conditions and circumstances in which it is implemented (van Berkel, 2016). In Slovenia, the use of contracting out of employment services has been very limited. With regards to the use of benchmarking and performance measurement, it is used extensively but in a ‘dialogical’ manner, without pay-for-performance elements, hereby leaving quite a large scope for manoeuvre at the regional and local levels, and in the end, in the front-level encounters with clients.

Key takeaways

Due to both the small size the country (around 2 mil. inhabitants) and the organisation of the PES within one state agency, the governance of the system of Slovenian PES is characterized by a short distance from central to the local level. Although the regional and local employment offices are measured and benchmarked according to performance indicators, the governance, unlike in many other countries, is trust- and dialogue based. It can thus be described as a ‘soft’ version of New Public Management, that has also only, so far, resulted in limited contracting out of employment services.

Part II

The activities and practices in local PES

In this part, we dive into the question of what is going on at the street-level in the local PES in Slovenia within the constraint of policies, legal frameworks and formal governance structures described in part I. Our approach and findings are inspired by governmentality studies (Foucault, 2008, Pultz, 2017) on the hand and on the STB literature on the other (Berkel et al., 2017; Brodtkin and Marston, 2013; Hupe et al., 2016). We show that on the one hand these policies and governance structures *do* matter in the sense that they shape the unemployment experience. On the other hand, we show how the actual practices in the local PES are also shaped by multiple other factors such as culture, (limited) resources, professional norms, local challenges on the labour market, etc. In this way, the street-level practices exemplify distinct interpretations and translations of formal rules. We start by mapping the formal rights and obligations of the unemployed when registering at the PES. In the following two sections we then describe the counselling practices and how these are experienced by the unemployed.

4 Rights and obligations of the unemployed

By Tjasa Redek, Marko Pahor, Mojca Svetek, Martina Rameša, Sabina Pultz, and Magnus Paulsen Hansen

4.1 Benefits

Under the current law, the eligibility for unemployment benefits is as follows: at least 6 months of employment in the last 24 months before becoming unemployed and below 30 years old gives 2 months of unemployment benefits, 10 months to 5 years of employment results in 3 months of unemployment insurance, 5 to 15 years of employment equals 6 months, 15 to 25 years of employment equals 9 months of unemployment benefits while those employed for more than 25 years are granted in between 12 and 25 months of unemployment depending of age of claimant (25 months if more than 58 years old more than 28 years of employment). The benefit is in the amount of 80% of the employment compensation for the first three months, 60% for the next 9 months and 50% thereafter. There is also a lower and upper limit to the compensation. If claimants lose their right to unemployment benefit and are eligible in terms of other income, they can apply for social assistance benefits, for which they also must be registered unemployed at the ESS.

Slovenia records one of the weakest financial incentives to move from unemployment to employment among the OECD and the EU, regardless the family type or wage level. Slovenia also faces strong inactivity traps, particularly for low-wage earners, lone parents and one-earner married couples due to taxes and reduced financial social assistance (Fialho and Høj, 2020; Laporšek, 2020). However, unemployment benefits and social assistance benefits FSA were financially aligned on the 1st of January 2020 reducing some disincentives (Fialho and Høj, 2020).

Table 2 Number of recipients of unemployment benefits, social assistance, pension by retirement due to disability among registered unemployed in Slovenia

	Unemployment benefits	Social assistance benefits	Pension by retirement due to disability	Total
2019	24.5%	38.7%	10.0%	
	18,464	29,102	7,556	75,292
2020	28.9%	43.7%	7.8%	
	25,236	38,148	6,849	87,283

Data: ESS

Table 2 shows the number of recipients of the various benefits. It shows that the group of unemployed is a diverse group of people and it also that is also a group of registered unemployed that are not receiving any benefits.¹⁰

4.2 Activation

The ESS services target the unemployed clients cover a variety of measures. These measures are structured in five types concerning education and training, workplace replacement and job sharing, employment incentives, job creation and self-employment (Redek, et al., 2020). Educational and training programmes is targeting both formal and informal competences, especially the long-term unemployed over the age of 50, people with lower education and young people. An example of a programme is the PUMO (Project learning for young and young adults), funded by the European Social Funds, that aims to help young people with obtaining an education and developing a professional identity. Other programmes are Inter-enterprise Education Centers (MIC) aiming to test the acquired knowledge of theory and practice while working in a specific job with the employer and certification of national professional qualifications (NPK) targeted young people who are not employed, are not in education or training (NEET) that through short trainings and tests provide somebody a certificate, for instance for a fork-lifter and the person is given a certificate).

Next to the measures focusing on training and education the ESS also manages several programmes enabling employment subsidies for specific target groups such as the long-term unemployed more than 50 years old (Zaposli.me/ Employ.me) and the Sustainable Youth Employment programme for unemployed young people. For unemployed further distanced from the labour market (receiving social assistance benefit or with disability status), the public works programme offers protected work to activate long-term unemployed. Finally, some programmes aim to support entrepreneurship and self-employment.

While many of these measures contain elements of up-skilling and increasing human capital, they are, in practice, a rather 'lean' version of social investment active labour market policies (ALMP), since they limited share of total welfare spending (Hrast Filipovič and Raka, 2017). In fact Slovenia is placed at the bottom of the EU countries, as the expenditures for the ALMPs accounted for only 0.16% of the GDP in 2016, from which very little is used on training (Fialho and Høj, 2020; Laporšek, 2020). Around two thirds of ALMP spending is financed by the European Social Funds (OP EKP 2014-2020). Meanwhile OECD has pointed to the need for increasing expenditures on adult learning for unemployed as well as employed since the labour force is having a high share of adults with poor problem-solving skills in technology-rich environments (48%) and a high share of workers in occupations facing a significant risk of automation (53%) (OECD 2020). Next to counselling, there are also a number of services related more directly to job search such 'speed dates' between employers and potential employees, 'job fairs' and 'open days' at ESS.

¹⁰ We explore the diversity of the group of unemployed further in chapter 6.

4.3 Obligations and sanctions

As described above, receiving unemployment benefits is conditional on living up to several obligations related to being an ‘active’ job-seeker. After registering in the register, every unemployed person, by signing the employment plan, assumes certain obligations of active job search, namely regular monitoring of job vacancies and timely application for them, appropriate response to invitations and referrals from the institution and other providers of measures, participation in job interviews at the invitation of the employer, institution or other contractors, involvement in labour market measures in order to increase employment opportunities, and accepting appropriate or suitable employment and striving to obtain employment at a job interview.

The rights and obligations of a job seeker are determined by the jobseeker plan, which is a form of contract between the job seeker and the PES. Still, the general obligations, mentioned above, remain. The jobseeker plan is made with the purpose and goal of improving employment opportunities for unemployed persons. The plan is described as a collaborative effort in which the jobseeker and the personal counsellor together define the employment goals and plan the necessary activities for his/her employment as soon as possible. When signing the plan the counsellor commit to monitor the implementation of agreements, provide timely information on job vacancies and other employment opportunities, provide relevant activation measures. The unemployed person, however, commit to fulfilling all activities arising from the employment plan within the agreed deadlines or to promptly and in a timely manner inform the personal adviser of changes that make it difficult or impossible to fulfil the agreements from the jobseeker plan. The fulfilment of the obligations is monitored through the regular meetings between the job seeker and counsellor.

Upon the first infringement of the obligations the job seeker/participant in the ALMP programme gets a warning and is invited to a hearing. Sanctions, including being stricken from the list of job seekers and losing all rights follow after the second infringement. Looking at the formal rules, Slovenia appears to be one of the strictest countries in Europe in terms of benefit eligibility criteria for unemployment insurance, in particular when it comes to job-search and monitoring requirements and benefit sanction provisions (Immervoll and Knotz, 2018).

The grounds for being sanctioned basically relate to breaches of the job-seeker plan and general requirements to being active. There are several reasons for unemployed being sanctioned, such as refusal to entering an active employment policy programme, refusal to accept appropriate or suitable employment or not trying to get a job during a job interview, provision of incorrect data regarding the eligibility for obtaining the status of the unemployed person, to engage in occasional or regular illegal employment, or refusal to sign the employment plan. Currently sanctions in ESS are given on a two-step basis, first a warning and decrease of unemployment benefits by 30 % for 2 months. This rule was introduced in 2017, which, seemingly, led to a steep decline in deregistrations due to

sanctioning as a result of two-step policy, an option which was afterwards removed (see Table 3).

Table 3 Reasons for deregistering unemployed

Deregistration reasons	2012	2014	2016	2018	2019	2020	2021
Employment	54.125	70.757	71.980	58.900	53.921	62.000	10.921
Sanctions	19.495	12.347	10.564	2.651	3.607	1.485	150
Inactivity	15.015	12.558	9.873	9.852	8.697	9.959	1.509
Own will and similar	8.260	7.102	7.507	7.876	7.778	7.566	1.033
Other status	461	1.156	631	1.183	1.726	2.839	548
within ESS							
Self-employment	4.195	3.193	2.876	2.642	2.351	2.404	347
Total	101.551	107.113	103.431	83.104	78.080	86.253	14.508
% deregistration due to sanctions	19,2	11,5	10,2	3,2	4,6	1,7	1,0

Source: ESS, 2021

Key take-aways

The chapter shows that the activities of PES are caught in between, on the one hand, policy intentions and, on the other hand, the local reality. Policies and programmes indicate a strong will to social investment and increasing the employability of the unemployed by increasing his or her skills and competences while the local PES in reality have very limited resources for such measures. A similar discrepancy can be found in the use of sanctions. While reforms of governments have called for more sanctioning, the actual deregistrations due to sanctions have been declining, due to unforeseen consequences of changes in legislation and the local practices in PES. Further, counsellors have professional arguments for, as well as the discretion to, limit sanctions.

5 Practices and counselling in PES

With inspiration from the theoretical framework of governmentality studies the unemployment experience is shaped by how unemployed people are governed. This entails not only official laws and rules, but also how they are administered in actual practices in concrete places. Hence, it is key to explore how the unemployed people experience and view meeting PES, how they think and feel about their counsellor and their obligations as unemployed people. We begin this section by giving a brief overlook of how the PES are delivered in practice, including characteristics of PES counsellors, their everyday work life as well an overview of the services at their disposal.

5.1 Characteristics of ESS Employees

Marko Pahor, Martina Rameša, Tjaša Redek, Mojca Svetek

Overall, counsellors are bound to the principles of counselling work as set in the Labour market regulation Act, Doctrine of counselling work and Manual on counselling work. The decision is (to an extent) upon them on setting the employability level that guides further counselling work, deciding on the inclusion to ALMP programmes, workshops, and other tailor-made services appropriate to specific sub-group of the unemployed.

The Employment Service of Slovenia employed 1,016 civil servants, of which 194 on projects. The number of employees financed from the state budget was 792 in December. 817 or 80% of all employees are employed on an open-end contract. 94.9% of all employees work on a full-time basis. 894 or 88% of them are women. Proportion of employees with at least a university degree (VII / 2 and more): 601 persons or 59% of all employees. Number of employees with the status of a disabled person: 27 persons or 2.7% of all employees (ESS yearly report, 2019).

Regional office Ptuj: "Practical Employment Promotion Program" "Find Vacancies"

Of all the employees in 2019, around 300 are counsellors. On average, each counsellor is taking care of 349 unemployed persons. The counsellors need to have at least the university degree in social work, social sciences and humanities, business, public administration, law or other relevant field and additional state exams (exam in administrative procedure, expert exam at ESS). Within counselling work counsellors can focus on different sub-groups (older, long-term unemployed, young unemployed). A group of counsellors is employed in the scope on EU-funded projects aimed at specific target groups (one project is aimed at vulnerable groups (older, long-term unemployed and lower education) and second project is aimed at young unemployed). Other counsellors usually cover unemployed who are immediately employable. There can be differences in organization of work which is responsibility of the RO/LO management and guided by their action plan. Specific counsellors also work with persons with disabilities, with health /social issues etc. There is an additional group of counsellors trained to offer in-depth career counselling, most of them are psychologists. According to the needs they apply psychometric tools. Another group of counsellors are dedicated to international cooperation trough EURES projects. There are also ESS offices for cooperation with employers. But it should be noted in smaller regional/local offices single counsellors can cover several of the fields and the division is usually possible in bigger offices.

5.2 Lifelong career orientation and services

Marko Pahor, Martina Rameša, Tjaša Redek, Mojca Svetek, and Sabina Pultz

Uncovering the technologies of power put in place to govern unemployed people involves looking into dominant understandings of problematisations as these are tightly linked to what solutions are offered. One of the key ideas in PES involves understanding the main task of the counsellors is providing *Lifelong career orientation*. In the following we unfold what this entails as well as how it is administered in practice as suggested by our empirical analysis based on both counsellor and jobseekers experience.

Waiting room, Ljubljana

Waiting area and offices, Ptuj

Overall, the services provided by the Employment Service in 2018 based on the Labour Market Regulation Act containing following elements: lifelong career orientation services, including labour market information, independent career management, basic and in-depth career counselling, learning career management skills. ESS provides lifelong career guidance services for school-going youth, and lastly, activities for persons with international protection in 2018.

Labour market information is a service that includes various forms of information on employment, education, training, financial assistance and other topics on the labour market in Slovenia and other EU countries, the EEA and the Swiss Confederation. The Employment Service provided information services through various channels: with the help of the Contact Center and Interactive Institutional Assistant (IZA), services provided by employees within the project Implementation of Services for the Unemployed, Other Jobseekers and Employers, through the Employment Service's website and web portal *PoiščiDelo.si*, in person at the Labour Offices and through social networks (FB, LinkedIn and others). Information services on EU employment opportunities, the labour market and other content related to the international mobility of workers were provided through the EURES job mobility portal, for which the Slovenian Employment Service also provides up-to-date information. Additional information was also available on the ESS national EURES website. This information also includes the possibility of financial support for mobility such as "Your first EURES job" and information on legal support for EU workers.

Lea: We also have kind of set of workshops, we prepared for those people. We call it the 'Job Club'. And it's especially designed for, I don't know, activate people, and help them, to realize what competence they have, for writing some additional information, possible limitation they have, and I must say, working with those small groups of people, actually have benefits for all of them.

Independent career management is a service with which the ESS encourages individuals to take an active approach to managing their own careers and solving unemployment, and for

this purpose offers various tools for independent decision-making and tackling labour market challenges. The services are available to all users via the ESS eServices free of charge. Assistance in the use of devices is provided by consultants in Career Centers and multichannel service providers within the project.

Basic career counselling is a service provided by the ESS' counsellors to provide systematic, individualized support to the individual in resolving unemployment and re-entering the labour market.

I: What kind of tools? Are they helping you with deciding?

Nikolaj: Yeah. They can be psychology assessment, Holland test which is a test for career goals. I think it's based on like a scheme system. They are not career goals, but employment goals and so on. So we have quite a few options, that (indistinct) also for the psychology graduates, so we have quite a lot of specialized tools. Questionnaires, interviews ... normal or guided interview. Then coaching. It really depends on the specific client, what difficulties to determine before meeting the clients, what do I think because I was a part of this ... education program from PES-career counseling course."

In-depth career counselling is an important service for the unemployed, where we perceive additional needs for motivation, obtaining appropriate professional qualifications and eliminating various situational and health barriers to employment and preventing the transition of the unemployed between the long-term unemployed and socially disadvantaged. In-depth career counselling offers unemployed people and jobseekers whose employment is at risk to help identify professional competencies and assess the interests, characteristics, abilities, potential barriers, and beliefs important for active participation in the labour market. With the support of career counsellors, the individual learns about the possibilities and opportunities in the environment, makes decisions about his career, decides to change limiting beliefs, and chooses activities to achieve the desired employment or career goals.

Learning career management skills is a service that includes various group forms of acquiring skills for learning about one's own interests and competencies, opportunities in the environment, learning to make decisions and achieving employment and career goals. This service is provided to unemployed persons and jobseekers whose employment is at risk.

The counselling process for persons with international protection is done at the Employment Service by two specially trained employment counsellors, who, in addition to their role as employment counsellors, also act as cultural mediators in integrating persons from this target group into the labour market and Slovenian society. In addition to working with the unemployed, the tasks of counsellors are also related to working with employers and cooperating with governmental and non-governmental bodies (ESS yearly report, 2019).

5.3 A counsellor's workday

Marko Pahor, Martina Rameša, Tjaša Redek, and Mojca Svetek

In order to get a deeper sense of how these conditions are actually put into practice, we begin here to address questions relating to the everyday life of the counsellor. Later, we will explore the “other side of table” addressing the everyday (work) life of the unemployed.

Typically, counsellor’s workday is divided into several segments. Typically, a counsellor that works only with unemployed does the following. The counsellor first obtains an insight into the data about job openings and data about the job seekers (may not be just the unemployed, they also occasionally work with those who are looking for improved job positions, a more stable job, etc.). By doing so, the counsellor obtains a good insight into the current (local/regional) labour market situation daily. This is followed by counselling, for example from 8-12 (as was in our case).

The clients have appointments, where a regular appointment would typically take 25-30 minutes, but the counsellor is independent in their evaluation of the time needed within the overall resources allocated. The services that are provided to the jobseeker differ and depend (as is described later for 3 most typical cases) on the typical problems that the unemployed faces. The counselling includes activities such as providing information about labour market based on individual’s needs, counselling, information about rights of jobseekers and unemployed, about their obligations, choosing activities (for example in-depth counselling, additional programs for unemployed, such as trainings, different workshops on or choosing more specific programs such as public works, etc.). These individual consultations are important also because the counsellor can “feel” the problems that the jobseeker is facing, which may go beyond their immediate problem of unemployment and help resolve those problems (we were provided with an example of a homemaker of 30 years, whose husband divorced her, she was without income and apartment and needed significantly more support). Some counselling is done also through telephone conversations and meetings are set up, whenever needed.

Offices at regional office Ljubljana

Part of the workday is devoted to preparing documentation. Practices vary from office to office, but generally, ESS is open for public 4 days in a week, Thursdays are closed for client. For basic career counselling the time limit for individual session is 25 minutes and 10 minutes of administration and reporting, for in-depth counselling 50 minutes per person and 10 minutes administration reporting. Depending on the size of the local office and division of work, counsellors may have different tasks – sometimes very clearly focusing on only 1 aspect (for example work with longer term unemployed) or may be involved in working both with unemployed and employers (as is the case in smaller offices). Despite the challenge of the workload, knowing well both the local employers and jobseekers is an advantage, because it can contribute to the speed of finding a match and how strong this match is.

Typically, one day per week is devoted to “new clients”, although this differs between small and large offices. All unemployed receive individual first meeting where employability is assessed and person’s plans, competences, work history and educations are discussed and noted. The individual employment plan is prepared stating rights and obligations; employment plan is later monitored and adapted if needed. The employability assessment guides further counselling - jobseeker can be guided to short workshops on career guidance/job search, can be included in ALMP programmes, jobseeker can get job referrals, preparation for the interview, can be guided to use ESS e-services. In case of more issues, person can receive in-depth counselling, rehabilitation counselling or health counselling, as there is cooperation with external institutions. Specific services and obligations are set individually and based on each group according to estimated employability (3 categories, based on counsellor’s estimation). Tailor-made programmes are adapted to each of the demographic category (older workers, first time job seekers, LTU etc.). Such an extended meeting is also used to evaluate, how much or how intense the counselling needed by a jobseeker will be. New clients are also invited to a group meeting/seminar, where several general information is provided. By doing so, then the individual meetings can focus on the individual in more detail.

5.4 Profiling

Marko Pahor, Martina Rameša, Tjaša Redek, Mojca Svetek, and Sabina Pultz

As already noted, counsellors enjoy a substantial extent of discretion, and so far, the profiling systems put into practice are also counsellor-based (rather than rule-based). There has been a development cutting the initial 7 risk categories down to 4 categories officially, however mostly three risk categories are used.

Employment Service of Slovenia (ESS) categorizes the unemployed persons into one of the following three categories:

- **directly/immediately employable** are motivated jobseekers with relevant skills and competences.
- **employable with additional activities** are jobseekers who lack relevant skills and competences or motivation to seek employment or might have manageable barriers to employment.
- **employable with intensive support** are jobseekers who require intensive support to be able to overcome complex barriers to employment.

There is a fourth group of **temporarily unemployable**, which is kept in a separate ESS register and includes those with overly complex barriers to employment due to critical problems with addictions, mental health, major social problems, or other problems that must be dealt with before trying to activate the person.

Figure 4 Categorization of the unemployed persons

Source: Redek et al., 2020.

In December 2019 14 % of the unemployed were categorized as directly employable, 44 % as employable with additional activities, and 42 % as employable with intensive support. The percentage of the temporarily unemployable is negligible (ESS, 2020).

This categorization is crucial in the selection of counselling and other activities to promote a swift transition into employment and prevent long-term unemployment.

Nikolaj: The first thing we check is employment possibilities for the client. If the person is directly employable or he has some needs that needs to be met before he's employable, or if he needs heavy support from our side. So three groups. Normally if a person is in a vulnerable group, so long-term unemployed over the age of 50 or 55 - depends on the action, without secondary school and so on, that means he's in the vulnerable group. And we offer more counselling, more in-depth counselling, shorter periods between counselling, more active labour policies options for the person and so on. And

of course, you have, as counsellor a difficult time deciding what to do with the client, we have things of our colleagues, which means at least one specialized counsellor, normally one from the field of psychology, which have at least 5-10 years' experience, is covering the things, and then we decide what the options will be and check the client from all points or as many as possible.

If the barriers to employment are identified, the jobseeker is transferred to 'in-depth career counselling'. In this case, he/she can be assisted by employment in-depth counsellor, in-depth counsellor psychologist, rehabilitation counsellor, or doctor counsellor. They provide holistic intensive counselling if basic counselling proves insufficient, they assess the motivation and employment goals, they take actions to overcome difficult social situations – cooperate with other institutions, use psychometric tools, provide a medical evaluation. They support and advocate for persons with significant obstacles for re-entering labour market. They can combine counselling with inclusion into LLL workshops and ALMP measures.

After each counselling session, the categorization of the unemployed is revisited. It can be changed if a substantial change in employability has been identified based on the acquired skills and competences, overcome barriers, or newly emerged barriers to employment. Accordingly, future counselling and other activities are adapted to fit the newly identified needs of the unemployed. At every session, the unemployed person is profiled i.e., around every 4 months.

Counsellors play a significant role in the categorization/profiling of the unemployed. To categorize the unemployed into one of the three categories, counsellors use administrative data collected at the registration with the ESS (gender, age, citizenship, educational attainment, work experience, disability status, etc.), collected through the Individual action plan questionnaire and the information collected during the first counselling interview.

During the first counselling interview (basic career counselling) a jobseeker and a counsellor prepare first individual action plan (sl., zaposlitveni načrt"), which includes employment and career goals as well as job-seeking activities, any additional activities the jobseeker is expected to participate in to increase his/her employability, and the job search area. A jobseeker regularly updates his/her action plan as a response to the changes in his/her employability and labour market conditions. If the barriers to employment are identified, the jobseeker gets additional support in preparing his/her individual action plan and is assisted by in-depth career counsellors.

The assessment of employability is a complex professional assessment, where it is necessary to consider many elements: 1) identified strengths (characteristics of the person) and opportunities (characteristics of the environment): knowledge, competencies, work experience, professional interests, realistic employment goals that are in line with the needs of the labour market, appropriate job search skills, sufficient activity and motivation of the person 2) identified individual traits and obstacles; in assessing whether a characteristic is a trait or an obstacle, an individual assessment is required on the basis of a comparison of the person's characteristics, his / her employment goals and the situation on the labour market

(e.g. high demand for unskilled workers with experience). In doing this, they follow the guideline of lifelong career orientation activities to: "*timely activate and empower individuals for independent, responsible, active and successful solving of unemployment problem*" (Doctrine 2011).

Additionally, counsellors (can) use a questionnaire to help with the setting of an individual employment/action plan. The questionnaire involves questions addressing previous experience, **important characteristics** (quick learning, persistence, orientation to detail, reliability, responsibility, self-confidence, communicativeness, organisational skills, creativity, leadership skills, physical fitness, adaptability, sociability, self-initiative, positivity, independence, ability to operate machines and use tools, manual skills), **desired work** (business with clients, office work, manual work, leadership, research, analysis data interpretation, operating machines, tourism, intellectual work, technical work, working with numbers, terrain work, helping others, sales, working outside, fieldwork, art, culture, media related work, services (hairdresser, stylist, security, masseur), hospitality, teaching, creative work, work organisation, work); **help with job search** (Finding the most appropriate job for me; support in active job search; information on entrepreneurship and self-employment possibilities; assistance in applying and preparing applications to job vacancies; information on available job posting for my occupation; help with acquiring job searching skills (workshops, classes); wanting to train for a different job or finish my education; help in preparation for a job interview; information on support (subsidies) for employment; information on occupations and LM possibilities; getting additional knowledge on short trainings/classes; Don't need assistance).

5.5 Digitalization

By Martina Rameša, Tjaša Redek, Marko Pahor, and Mojca Svetek

The level of digitalization is naturally of relevance to the Hecat project, hence we will briefly note a few remarks about the digital infrastructure of ESS.

ZP-net is used by counsellors and ESS employees for easier guidance of unemployed. The ZP-net application enables the entry of individuals' (unemployed and job-seekers) data, tracking and analysis of all important data. The application allows tracking of an unemployed person and a job seeker from the point of registration, through the process of the preparation of an employment plan, his/her inclusion in active employment policy measures, counselling by specialized counsellors, job-matching and through to the termination of keeping records in the Employment Service. Of other relevant digital resources, there are:

- Poiščidelo (engl. »Find a job«, www.pois.cidelo.si): The »Poišči delo« offers the following services to unemployed and job-seekers: The web-based tool also allows (1) access to necessary data for finding a job 24 hours/day, (2) stimulates taking on

more responsibility, and (3) more independence in finding a job. It also offers online Career tools and advice and faster and easier services (service My advisor).

- E-svetovanje (<https://esvetovanje.ess.gov.si/>) – e-counselling: personality tests, competences test, vocation, etc., job search tips, labour market information.
- Moja izbira (engl. »my choice«, on-line tool to support occupational education, developed by Centre for occupational education, ESS cooperated, <https://www.mojaizbira.si/>)
- Kam in kako (engl. »where and how« that supports career guidance, <https://www.ess.gov.si/ncips/kam-in-kako>)
- Search & match engine (being prepared)

The employment service of Slovenia offers several e-tools for both employers and employees, which are available through their introductory webpage. The intensity of use varies with age and education. Over 37% of those aged 25-34 years use the platform, while on the other hand only 8% of those aged 55-64 years. The data also show that there are more users with higher education, for example those with at least secondary education represent in total 75% of users. The analysis of user-satisfaction shows that over 40% of users, regardless of their education, use the pages weekly. There is some variation in frequency of use by education – those most educated more often (25% of all users) report daily use, while those least educated are also those, who slightly more often reported never using the pages (around 7% of all those, who only had primary education). The pandemic has generated a push towards digitalizing PES further.

5.6 Meeting PES: Profiling, individual plan and discretion in practice

Investigating the unemployment experience also entail considering the lived experiences in concrete, institutional settings, and this involves the bodily experience of coming to local PES offices. As can be viewed in the pictures above from local PES offices, the atmosphere resembles jobcentres elsewhere in the world.

From the unemployment literature, we know that walking into jobcentres or other local offices of unemployment can be associated with negative emotions. In concordance with this, Bojana describes that coming into the local PES office is associated with a “bad vibe”:

In general, when you come there, the energy is super bad. I'm very sensitive and intuitive, so I can feel people there and there are people that are probably in real struggle, having a hard time so just standing there in line, it's horrible. It's not good.

Only few of the interview participants note the atmosphere, however.

From the vantage point of the interview participants, the first meeting and the initial impression of the PES is predominantly characterized by answering multiple standardised questions. For some, it is surprising that these data are not already registered electronically. While the counsellors use this information (among other sources) to evaluate which profiling category the unemployed person belongs to, the profiling system is not described by the unemployed persons as this process is unknown to them. Instead, all the interview participants describe taking part in developing an individual plan in collaboration with the counsellor.

The overall satisfaction with the job plan is lower compared to other measures of satisfaction (3.51/5) (Kurdija, Ignjatović, & Zupančič, 2019), followed by a little more positive rating of the helpfulness of the active employment programs in the job seeking (3.63/5). In general, the interpersonal relationship with the counsellor is rated the best as operationalized in two items, helpfulness of the counsellor (4.34/5) and informativeness of the counsellor (4.33/5). The qualitative analysis largely supports this finding and in the following we will unfold in more detail the reasons for these evaluations.

One of the key characteristics of enduring conditionality in the Slovenian employment policies is based on the contractual instrument of the individual employment plan (also see page 35). In the following we unfold how both the unemployed persons and counsellor experience working with this tool. As noted, the interview participants are unaware of profiling categories, however the plan is important to them and a majority explain that the plan is made in collaboration with the counsellor and to a substantial extent reflect and show understanding of actual circumstances. The content of the plan varies quite a lot among the interview participants, mirroring counsellor discretion. None of the interview participants describe having too many obligations, such as having to apply for too many jobs or being forced to do meaningless activities. Also, by the counsellors, the individual plan is described as a flexible instrument, however, in all cases to some extent securing active job search:

Hana: By the law they have to be active, so they have to search for a job, but the number and what activities, what timeline that depends on the counsellor. So as a counsellor you have a lot of discretion to modify the way people do their obligations. So it's really.. you don't have to be .. you have to be flexible.

I: You, as a counsellor, have to define a lot for the individual unemployed. Do you make a contract or?

Hana: Yes, a contract but I try to explain that in my first counsellor session, that they are responsible for their life, and it is better for them to decide what activities and when they will do it. 'Cause if you decide for them, there is a lack of motivation. So you have to get some degree of them saying 'okay, it's doable for me'.

Hana underlines the importance of making the plan in collaboration with the unemployed people because that is a way of securing realistic goals and compliance. Hana also notes that he has “a lot of discretion” that makes it possible to match the plan with the level of motivation and responsibility on the jobseeker’s side.

Across the interviews with counsellors, discretion is often emphasized, and it is often valued making them capable of doing what they see fit in relation to particular people. For many of the counsellors, they choose to work within social work to help people and getting sufficient space to manoeuvre is key to them:

Hmm.. It is very important to have individual approach, to know what's good with your own clients. To see what they need, what they want, what kind of experience they have and are they ready for the labour market or no? And so, I have this freedom to choose the ways, I would say, how to deal or how to work with this kind of client. For example I have clients who needs to work on some personal issues first, and then they are ready for entering the labour market. Perhaps .. I have a client, she is a housewife and she was for 30 years, then her husband left her, and she lost her house. She never worked. She finished her school, but never worked. So she has no working experience. This kind of clients are not ready for the labour market. She needs to deal with her personal problems first, to set her life together. So we have programs, and we can .. we have really good programs for this kind of person, who just need to learn life, to live, to settle their finances and so on. And to learn how to write a letter, how to write a resume. It's a very complex thing. And we have a problem, and I have the freedom to choose that this kind of client can go to this kind of program, and then I can try; Is she prepared for an interview? So, with this client I went to the employer, I was there with her so I could see how she was presenting herself; was she ready or not? So I can decide how to proceed further. So our .. we have this kind of freedom to go with the client.

Rather than imposing standardised demands of activation Hana explains that she has the capacity to help her client in a much broader sense than merely job search. To learn career management skills there are a few other competencies or issues that needs to be addressed and Hana can *take the woman's experience and situation into consideration*. Rok supplements and notes: *"I can decide for everything. So, my knowledge is my feeling, what will I do with the client. So, if he has some kind of problems, and I decide if I will... I will put him to a doctor or not."* Working as counsellor involves understanding people's situations and the circumstances they live under. As Rok puts it:

Let's say, the minimum wages are very low, not so... You don't get a lot less with social help, people just calculate, you have two children, they have free kindergarten, the rent is lower. People calculate it, and then maybe they decide.

From the outset he identifies and respects the agency of his clients, and when they do not pursue finding a job at minimum wage while having caring responsibilities, he uses that as a meaningful ground for not pushing them or forcing them either into a low-quality job, nor out of the unemployment system.

This was also raised in the focus group. An advantage of focus groups is that existing taken-for-granted understandings as well as negotiations about these become visible in the data. Here, Helena, also noted:

Because if they are calculating, if they don't see their future in the long run, why would they work? They get the minimum wage, no security, contracts 1

month after 1 month and so on, and then employer 'hmm I don't need you anymore.' Why would they work?

From the above, it is evident that the counsellors consider labour market dynamics and incentives built into these.

The individual plans overall make sense to the interview participants. I.e. David, who receives social assistance and is registered in the unemployment register, has spent the last year finishing his bachelor's degree while officially being unemployed. His counsellor has not made any other demands in terms of job search beyond finishing his degree: *“She said there's no responsibilities, but she'll be happy if "you call me and tell me something about you, if you got a job or something.”* Similarly, Erika describes that her individual plan considers her actual circumstances, her past and work experience as well as it is shaped by current wishes for a job. While she is educated as a nurse, she does not want to look for a job in this field, and her counsellor respects that decision and does not try to challenge that perspective:

But once she excluded me from looking for jobs as a nurse, because she saw that I lack experience. I never worked as a nurse, so that wasn't the right choice of schooling. So, she said, okay we are not going there. She never forced me or required me to get a job as a nurse, as according to my education.

While Erika also notes that she does not have experience working as a nurse and that might also pose a potential barrier finding a job within this field, it is noteworthy that the counsellor takes vantage point according to her current ideas about what kind of work she would like to do. Other interview participants like Danica does not have an experience that the plan is developed together with the counsellor. On the contrary, she feels that the plan is predefined: *“Usually they print, and it is all prepared before we come. When we come, sometimes he shares it with us, it is already on the table. And then we go through it.”*

Almost all interview participants describe being compliant in relation to the plan, however there are some exceptions. As a rule, the unemployed people must follow the plan agreed upon and in Vera's case that involves applying for job vacancies suggested by PES, however she has not complied with this:

Vera: I have to respond to or propose job vacancies that the unemployment office forwards to me. For example, I got vacancies for the financial industry, I did not apply. I really don't like working with figures.

I: Okay. So, what then happened, when you didn't reply?

Vera: Until now? Nothing.

Vera did a degree in economics, but she is very decisive about not wanting to work within that field anymore. No more numbers and figures, as she says. Now she is looking for work

that provides her with “colour” as she puts it. While she does comply with the demands, there has been no consequences of this behaviour. It seems that she is governed more “softly”.

From the interviews and focus groups with counsellors, it was also clear that sanctioning was rarely in the table. In part because of the understanding of people’s circumstances and in part because it has been a bureaucratic burden to justify the use of sanctions:

They can be (sanctioned, ed.), but it's not that easy to sanction. They are quite aware of that.

Okay, so sometimes they don't follow the plan and that's okay?

Sometimes I know they have a real good excuse why they didn't follow the plan, sometimes we talked about it, and we can give them another chance to make up. So, depends on the person and how serious he/she is.

In this case being serious refers to being an active jobseeker. Similarly, another interview participant describes being met with a high level of tolerance. One of the interview participants, Milan, openly discuss working conditions with potential employers and this is problematised by his counsellor who Milan paraphrases in the following: *“You know, these are not the types of questions you would ask today”* (..) *She said when you get an interview, you don't ask these questions.”* There is no mentioning of potential economic sanctioning of him continuing asking critical questions, however. Also, Milan does not explicitly criticize his counsellor for offering that feedback, he turns his frustration toward the capitalist organizing of the Slovenian society and points towards revolution as a way of solving the situation (he is aware that most likely, this will not happen, though).

An issue identified by some of the interview participants is the lack of knowledge about their specific professional fields within PES generally, and among counsellors specifically. While this does constitute a barrier, the interview participants who raise this issue do not criticize or blame counsellors, as they do not expect this to be the case. Marjan, says: *“They (the counsellors, ed.) are not so much informed especially about IT.. but I don't blame them .. I mean, I can't blame them because also lack of knowledge about IT area.”*

In terms of shedding light on how the interview participant experience various services and measures of activation offered at PES, a surprisingly large proportion has taken German courses as part of a potential job search strategy that involves searching for jobs in Austria. This is especially the case of bordering regions. All of the interview participants who have done that still note that their level of German is probably not good enough to work in Austria. However, working conditions (in particular in terms of wages) in Austria seem to be better and therefore many of them keep it as a plan b or c.

Another interview participant, Vera, also compares her current experience with PES with one 20 years ago. Vera describes that back then, there was a plethora of opportunities:

20 years ago, I was very satisfied because I was given many training courses in the field of calligraphy, public performing, public speaking, English language as well, computer science. And this enabled me then, 20 years ago, to start my own business.

In comparison, she feels that there are not many opportunities to get support or new qualifications from within the system and she sees that as a problem.

5.7 Counsellor/client relationship

A majority of the interview participants describe the level of contact as appropriate and that they have a dynamic interaction with their counsellor, often when they in addition to the standardised scheduled meetings also call to discuss new openings and new relevant courses. Approximately half of the interview participants describe getting calls from their counsellor with specific job openings and all of them values this sort of concrete and customised contact and help. Here Milan, 60 years, describes getting helpful information:

You have a feeling that he cares about you. That he is just sitting there for 8 hours, no, talking to him you feel he is working hard, and trying to find jobs for you. Talking to you in numbers, data, that you had to search for online, somewhere in the background. He will tell you openly, and that's very important for me.

Accordingly, another interview participant, Klara, has just found a job, that she is about to embark on at the time of the interview and in this case, the counsellor has referred her to that job opening:

I have a counsellor and I work well with her. Every three months we have a meeting. She checks how I am. The last time I was without a job was in June of this year. I came back and applied. And my counsellor took things I can do and know how to do. They sent me potential employments, so I can check offers for me. And then I apply, and if I get lucky, I get invited to the interview.

Later in the interview, Klara describes the particular job in question as “*a wish of mine since I was little.*” Most of the interview participants describe their counsellors as understanding, friendly and competent. The level of understanding is in part based on how counsellors have sufficient discretion to make realistic demands. For instance, David, 27, receives social welfare and he is registered in the employment register. He has been delayed in terms of graduating as a physiotherapist and he described that in his employment plan it is stated that he should only begin active job search after finishing his thesis. Hence, for more than half a year he did not have to actively search for a job. Many of them feel lucky about their counsellor and inscribe the competence and care to the individual counsellor rather than on the general system. According to David, there are still stereotypes about a more negative representation of counsellors as somebody who is mainly bureaucratic and controlling:

Yeah, the counsellor was very great. Maybe it was also because she was younger, and I can't actually know, but she really seemed to care. She was always looking for a conversation on everything. So, very helpful. I didn't get the classic stereotype that they have no time or no sympathy, and that they just give up and don't care for anything. I don't know, I got a good counsellor maybe, I'm not sure.

Across the positive evaluations of counsellors, many of them underline that they “understand”, “really care”, and, even, has become “an extra family member” such as Jana unfolds:

We have a very good connection. I can call or chat with her normally. Like a family member. She's not an annoying person, always calling and asking, “did you do that, did you do this, why didn't you do that”. She understands when I tell her that it's very hard. She even knows that it's hard for a young person under 30 to get a job.

Jana explains the good connection by referring to understanding and lack of control from the counsellor. She feels like she is met with respect, and later in the interview she notes about the counsellor “*She never pushed me into something I didn't wanted.*”.

Many of the interview participants experience that they do not have to document their job search for surveillance purposes, however more of the interview participants who also had experience with PES earlier on, note that this constitutes a change. IP remarks that excessive documentation was the case 10 years ago:

this job counsellor, she's not asking for them (documentation for job search). I have them with myself, I have in my notes, which companies I contacted, ehh .. I have this list with me, but she never asks me for that. The last job counsellor did ask for this.

On the other hand, some people mention that they would like to have more contact with counsellors, and they feel left to themselves. Karmen, 27, experiences a lack of support from the system, and she feels that the contact with the counsellor does not involve an understanding of her situation:

My counsellor didn't even look at my CV, which I have. And I think that's, you know, wow, or something. Yea so, I didn't really get much out of the system that way. They didn't even send me like anything in the last month.

She elaborates about feeling left to herself and that the main interest in the system is trying to understand why someone was not successful in finding a job rather than proactively helping people to find jobs:

Well ideally, I would have a meeting sooner than in half a year, from the first one. That's concerning to me. I think that just kind of give the impression, that 'just don't search for a job'. Like 'here is the money, come back in six months, we'll talk about why you didn't get a job'. And then, you can leave another 6 months. Which is weird to me.

While Karmen does not experience being in a particular profiling category, presumably she is categorised among the “immediately employable” and thus her reflections might to some extent reflect that she belongs to that category. Presumably, she is perceived of as self-reliant and resourceful by the counsellor and able to find a job on her own. However, she experiences that the lack of contact should suggest that she will not be able to find a job and that is discouraging to her personally, as well as it making her critical of the system. To some extent that shows the limitations of profiling systems and the unintended negative effects they also have.

Some of our interview participants have had prior experience with PES and one interview participant noted that PES once was dominated by an understanding of unemployment with historical links to the past in which the unemployment rate was extremely low. The low unemployment rate was associated with an understanding that anybody who wanted to work, could find a job and that used to impact on how counsellor acted but not anymore:

At that time - not to be offensive in any way - but most of them were older ladies working from the time of former Yugoslavia. They didn't understand or believe you, that you can't get a job.

Demands for excessive documentation is no longer the case and in general, there does not seem to be a lot of mistrust or suspicion against the unemployed people.

Posters, Regional Office Ljubljana “Who can register with the employment center?”, “Application and admission procedure”, “Kam in Kako, Where and how?”

The interviews with counsellors also provide some insight into the use of sanctions. Rebeka points to the paradoxical situation that on the hand the government has emphasized the need to sanction while the rules have made it harder:

In the past, it was, and it's like the Government wants us to sanction a lot, but at the same time it became really difficult to sanction. When I started working here, one thing that they [the unemployed] didn't do, was already enough to unregister them. And now there has to be proof. And also for everything, I mean something we have to that we didn't in the beginning, we have to call them here, to give them the option to explain themselves, what happened. So the whole procedure, even if the persons never shows up here, it mostly takes half a year to have the option to really make that sanction. Not that much

anymore, because it's really a lot of work, and it takes a lot of time for all these procedures.

Also, the counsellors often do not find it meaningful to use sanctions and thus do what they can to avoid it. Hana, for instance, notes that

... especially with long-term unemployed people you can't explain that some rule or penalty will help them get motivated or solve the problems they have. Their problems are so complex, that it's not possible. So if I decide to sanction someone for six month or something it doesn't work. It doesn't give you a solution.

Hana thus chooses to 'concentrate on the positive'. Helena describes how she tries to keep a collaborative relation before sanctioning:

... it is always; we talk first, we try.. I give advice. I give first a friendly advice, and then [laughs]. Because I need arguments to why, and if the client don't cooperate, collaborate, if the client doesn't make a step forward there are some ... I need to follow some procedures.

The quote also illustrates the substantial discretion counsellors have in making decisions related to sanctioning.¹¹ In this regard, Hana, explains how the decision is based on 'experience':

There is always an argument that you can defend, so if you argue good then the penalty is not necessary. We have control and supervisor and so on, but if you know what you are doing, and you do some measure with people in activities, then they can see that the person is trying but maybe not in the way they think.

As Hana emphasizes, understanding the person provides the best foundation for making good decisions and backing these up by professional arguments.

Key take-aways

While this section highlights various resources at PES, we draw attention to the scarce resources, also reflected in the counsellor's high workload. We identify an incentive to ration and profiling tools have proven useful to do that.

Among counsellors we see a strong professional ethos of care and enabled by a relatively flexible system, counsellors can work independently using their discretion rather than imposing the same standardised demands on all citizens. Customized individual plans that consider personal, social and economic circumstances. There are substantial differences in the experience of PES from unemployed people. We find that while some people experience they get sufficient support, a minority lacks contact with PES and feel left to themselves. This might mirror the differentiated governing in relation to risk categories embedded in the existing profiling system.

¹¹ We explore the issue of discretion further in chapter 5.

Part III

Labour market and job-seeking

In this part, we investigate the socio-economic dynamics and characteristics of the Slovenian labour market as well as the characteristics of the unemployed from a statistical perspective. We focus on three phenomena that we see as of particular importance to understand the needs and challenges of the unemployed as well as the challenges of the Hecat to visualize the labour market and to underpin pathways towards quality jobs. The three phenomena are long-term unemployment, the prevalence of various forms of precarious work and, finally, the role of the shadow economy. We begin by introducing the statistical data and move on to explore the qualitative data to develop nuances and the unemployment experience into these perspectives. In the last two chapter (9 and 10) we provide some insights to the participants' reflections on the Hecat platform and the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic.

6 Characterizing the unemployed

6.1 Numbers and figures

In this section we look into who are the unemployed and zoom in on the long-term unemployed. Looking at the situation before the Covid-19 crisis, the unemployment rate in Slovenia was among the lowest in the EU (see figure 5).

Figure 5: Unemployment rate in EU countries as % of total active population, 2019 (Pahor, et al., 2020)

Source: Data derived from Eurostat, 2019

While unemployment rate is relatively low it also covers significant regional differences going from the lowest rates in the west to highest in east of Slovenia (Fialho and Høj, 2020, see figure 6). Not surprisingly, one of the most vulnerable groups in Slovenia are the unemployed, who face high at-risk of poverty rates, remaining stable even after the crisis at 45.6 % in 2018 (Hrast et al., 2020: 694).

The changes in the economy are not reflected only in the number of unemployed, but also in the structure of unemployed, where economic crises, or booms impact different groups in the labour market differently. With the levels of unemployment also the gender structure, age structure and education structure change. Figure 7 reveals the changing structure of the unemployed from the gender perspective. Before the 2008 the share of women among the unemployed was higher, but crisis-related lay-offs, which were more present in the manufacturing sector first, impacted heavily the gender structure. During the recovery, the share of men declined and primarily also the absolute number of unemployed men.

Figure 6 Unemployment rate (Registered) by regional offices (where UPs are registered), XII 2020 (Pahor, et al., 2020)

Data: ESS

Figure 7: Gender structure of the unemployed: number of unemployed men and women (Pahor, et al., 2020)

Source: Data derived from Zavod RS za zaposlovanje, 2020a

Figure 8 below reveals the age structure of the unemployed. Following the economic recovery around 2014, the age structure of the unemployed significantly changed. The share

of those aged 50 and more increased from 31% in 2013 to even 39% in 2019 and remained high (Pahor, et al., 2020). The Covid-19 crisis lowered the share (but not absolute number) of older unemployed because of the increased inflow of younger unemployed. In 2020 the number of older unemployed (50+) actually increased from 29,3 thousand to 31.7 thousand, but the number of unemployed in other age groups increased significantly more – by 13 thousand until June 2020.

Figure 8: Age structure of the unemployed in % of all unemployed (Pahor, et al., 2020)

Source: Data derived from Zavod RS za zaposlovanje, 2020a

Despite the positive developments in the Slovenian labour market up to the Covid-19 crisis, the share of the long-term unemployed remains at 2.3% of the active population (20-64 years) and represents 43.7% of all unemployment, which is below the EU-28 and EU-15 averages, but it is nonetheless high and represents a challenge, especially considering that the structure of the long-term unemployed (see Figure 9). Those with lowest education (ISCED 0-2) represent the majority of the long-term unemployed (Eurostat, 2019).

Figure 9: Long-term unemployment (LTU – more than one year) and very-long term unemployment (VLTU – more than two years) as percent of all unemployed in Slovenia and EU28 (Pahor et al., 2020)

Source: Data derived from Eurostat, 2020

During the upswing and shortage of mid-level qualified workers with occupation-specific knowledge rather than generic skills vacancies were increasingly being filled by hiring foreigners. Already prior to the crisis, unemployment fell at a slower pace for older, low-skilled, and long-term unemployed (see figure 7). The long-term unemployment rate also fell at a slower pace for older workers compared to other age categories (Fialho and Høj, 2020).

Figure 10: Structure of unemployed by duration of unemployment (Pahor, et al., 2020)

Source: Data derived from Zavod RS za zaposlovanje, 2020a

Besides lacking the demanded skills, which is also caused by limited inclusion of low-qualified adults in lifelong learning (Laporšek, 2020), long-term unemployment is also

caused by poor economic incentives for many families and individuals to work. According to Laporšek, Vodopivec and Vodopivec unemployment benefits and cash transfers, coupled with high tax wedge, create one of the weakest financial incentives to move from unemployment to employment in the EU (Laporšek et al., 2019)

6.2 Activated unemployed? Blame and shame

Following the active turn in employment policies in Europe, activation policies have also to some extent been incorporated into the Slovenian PES. The active turn is associated with the construction of the active jobseeker turning unemployed people into someone who takes responsibility for her situation. This has also been termed the individualisation of unemployment, and while such liberal norms are more pervasive in other (western) countries, these liberal normative ideals of independence and self-sufficiency are also present in the data, however not as significantly as in other countries. This might reflect the fact, that Slovenia combines different employment measures and in general characterized a soft paradigm as explained above.

Scholars have established a link between the activation paradigm and the unemployment experience, connecting it to increased responsibility of the self with self-blame (Sharone, 2013; Pultz, 2017). For the current purpose, we are interested in analysing further how unemployed people experience receiving money from the state as this is a way of beginning to understand how unemployed people are looked upon and evaluated in the Slovenian society.

For the most part, the interview participants receive either unemployment benefits or social welfare without mentioning having any troubles receiving money from the state. As Marjan answers when asked about how he feels about getting money from the state: *“Ehh I’m not thinking much about this, I’m looking for a job.”* Inherent in this comment and in a multitude of other interviews, it seems there is a tight connection between receiving money as justified by an active job search.

The unemployment literature covers the impact on unemployment on internalized stigma and shame across a wide array of national contexts (Creed and Muller, 2006; Creed et al., 2014; Pultz, 2018) however to our knowledge, so far no studies have been made addressing these issues in a Slovenian context. Interview participants do describe that being unemployed is associated with lack of morals, of inactivity, and of being a burden on the state, however this seems to be less pervasive compared to other countries. Here Karmen refuses to collect unemployment benefit despite being eligible for it because she prefers not being under the state’s authority and also it goes against her morals to receive money from the state. She prefers being self-reliant (could also go to that section):

Yea, I don’t receive benefits.

Okay, so you are not entitled to it?

No, I am. I just don't like it. I have very high moral values, and if I am able not to receive benefits, then I will do that. I know a lot of people that do exactly that (receive unemployment, ed.), but I just don't. Like, why would you do that? So I don't. (...) I guess one of the reasons also, why I didn't want to receive benefits is because I know some people where the system wanted them to get a specific job. Go to an interview, and you had to take it. And I don't need any more money, and I want to find a job that I want to work at for a long term. So why would I put myself in that situation? Then I would actually have to take a job that I wouldn't like.

According to Karmen, her morals prevent her from receiving money from the state, as she thinks that any person who in some way or the other has the possibility not to receive should be self-sufficient. Later in the interview she notes: “.... *because maybe there is somebody that need more money than me.*” Also, receiving money from the state comes with a particular obligation in her mind, that she could be forced to take a job against her personal wish and will. Staying out of receiving money from the state is thus associated to a lack of agency on her behalf.

Jana on the other hand, does receives unemployment benefit, but she would much prefer to make her own money, as she feels it is shameful for her to get money from the state rather than contributing to it. Asked about whether she feels that it is embarrassing to get money from the state, she answers:

Yes sometimes. No in the beginning I did feel this all the time, but then I did look at others, because there are people that are maybe younger than me, that are taking much longer time on this money and then do nothing to get a job. In my case I do a lot of things to get a job, but I have not had any luck.

In the quote it becomes clear that Jana believes that receiving money from the state is justifiable if she works hard to try to find a job. She positions herself in contrast to people who receive the money without putting in an effort to get out of the system again. Dealing with stigma by associating it with others has also been documented elsewhere among unemployed people engaging in manifold othering mechanisms (Pultz, 2018). There is one “othering process” distinguishing between people who work and unemployed people, but internally in the unemployed category, there are also “othering mechanisms” differing between deserving and undeserving unemployed people”. Along similar lines, Jana describes so-called scroungers multiple times during interviews which is linked to her active positioning among the deserving unemployed people and her views on what constitutes a deserving unemployed person:

They don't want to do nothing to get a job. Even having 10 years of support from the country, and they do nothing. That's why I support that, that they need to check if you do something.

She is hesitant to receive money from the state because of a self-sufficiency ideal captured here: “*There is no job I didn't take, because I don't like taking money from the country. I like*

having my own money, that I earn. “The justification is also linked to an openness towards all types of jobs and not being overly selective or picky.

Overall, interview participants vary in terms of identifying reasons for being unemployed mainly within oneself or looking outward in society. Only a few are prone to self-blame and all the participants identify reasons embedded in dynamics in the labour market that exist outside of themselves. Here, Jure, who suffered from a heart attack 3 years ago describe 1) how many open positions in Slovenia involves physical labour and 2) that a lot of older people remain in the labour market instead of going off on pension leaving positions open for young Slovenian workers:

I think that in my case it is my health condition. For me that is it. Because if I would be allowed to be physical, I would get a job instantly, because warehouses are always looking. Physical jobs are always open here in my region. So yeah, I think that is mainly the reason. And I think a lot of problems in Slovenia has to do something with that, because a lot of people that would need to retire don't want to retire. And a lot of young people like me don't get a chance to work. I think that is quite the problem here in Slovenia, in a lot of positions.”

He continues along the same lines:

I saw that there are men over fifty or something ... okay fifty is an okay age. But you see people that are sixty and up that are still working. You see they are strong, especially in some markets. A lot of old people are still working, and you apply for the job as a cashier, and you don't get it because they just don't go to retirement. The state should do something about that, they should take care of the elderly. I think that is the problem mainly.

6.3 Ambiguous role of skills and education

For many unemployed people the role of skills and education are also somewhat of a mystery on the Slovenian labour market, despite the fact that a significant part of job vacancies are lower skilled. Almost all interview participants mention college or university degrees as playing an influential role in accessing quality jobs on the labour market. Many of the interview participants mention that having university degrees has become increasingly important in order to be able to apply for positions, also in regard to jobs in which the tasks would not necessarily need qualifications acquired at higher education. As Milan here jokes:

When I first came to the labour market - or to the unemployment office - there was a general feeling that any employment required a degree. And I was joking, slowly they will ask the cleaning-ladies to present their degrees.

In addition to changed and increasing demands of educational merits, many of them describe that they have not worked within their educational field, and they do not necessarily

expect to do this in the future either. Karmen, does not at the time of the interview have a college degree and she identifies this as a major problem in relation to landing a job within administration:

Right now, I feel like I'm going to have to go to college at some point, to get to where I want to be. Which I don't think is the only option, but I'm not sure. It's like, what else should I do? Because the college thing has just been - like - everybody has college degrees, and if everybody has a college degree, it's kind of useless. And you don't need a college degree to do a lot of things. Like, most of my friends they've graduated college, and literally 1 of them works in their field. And he's a doctor. Nobody else works in the field, they went to college for. So I don't really see, because it's been engraved in my mind for so long, I just feel like I have to go to college. I'm not worth anything on market, without a college degree. And it would be nice to know the alternatives.

She feels pressured into taking a college degree even though she also critically remarks that getting a college degree in the current labour market does not allow her to stand out. To her, it feels like that a college degree is the minimum barrier and without a degree she has not been able to cross that barrier. In addition to lowering her labour market opportunities, she also feels that it is linked with a low sense of worth.

In addition to educational qualifications as key currencies in the Slovenian labour market, other categories also gravely affect labour market opportunities. Especially health issues seem to play a large role and whether the person has a disability status affects labour market opportunities quite a lot. Klara was diagnosed 6 years ago, and she experiences discrimination on the labour market, mainly because a lot of the employers are unaware of the many resources that are associated with employing a person with disability status and therefore, she tried to hide her medical condition:

The three years have been the worst that I can imagine. Yeah, these relate to a disability. I am not sure why people are afraid, why employers don't want to employ people with a disabled status. I can say for myself, that I am hardworking, I want to go out and show off. I will try to look for a job, but since my diagnosis from six years ago, I've been without work for a year and a half. Out of the whole six years. Before I was afraid to tell it. I was hiding it, despite it being obvious. It shows, it's obvious. I was afraid of how people were going to take it.

Being unemployed is in itself not attractive and health issues put increasingly pressure on people. Among the interview participants it is common to reflect on whether to be open or hide health issues as there does not seem to be a good understanding towards this group of people on the labour market.

6.4 Confidence and doubting oneself

Multiple rejections can lead to a growing self-doubt, both in terms of questioning own's competences as well as questioning decisions about education, or other life choices that impact the current employment situation (Pultz, 2017). Erika, 48 years old, describes that job searching involves "selling oneself" and she remarks that the various rejections has perhaps challenged this ability: "*Perhaps I cannot sell my experience well enough, because I doubt my abilities to perform the job required.*" Also, Jana describes the emotional toll of receiving a multitude of rejections.

So I did search everywhere and send job request around everywhere. No one didn't get it, but it was really hard. There were no answers back. One month I did send almost 200 requests, and there was only one answer. That was very sad, and then you get a little bit depressed and you ask yourself, do I really need to do that, am I good enough..

However, later in the same interview, she mentioned that she normally has an optimistic outlook: "*I would say, it's going to be better tomorrow. I didn't stop sending job request, I send everywhere. I even got two invitations for interviews under corona (indistinct).*"

Keeping up spirits and maintaining optimism even in the face of multiple rejections is required in order to be able to find a job according to Klara: "*Positivity. You need to be positive, communicative skills, optimistic. If it doesn't happen today, it will happen tomorrow. And a little bit of luck.*". The optimistic outlook is also linked to an experience of being self-confident which is also required in the job search: "*In my case, I would say you need confidence, and selfconfidence, to show and to tell them without the paper, to just say "I can do that". You have to show or prove yourself.*"

Karmen, 27, regrets not having finished a college degree despite, because it makes her ineligible for a number of jobs, she feels capable of holding: "*The thing that is holding me back is that I decided not to go to college. That was a very stupid mistake. I might pursue it later, but right now my finances are draining, draining, draining. So you know, I have to have a job first.*" Her current financial situation does not allow her to pursue getting a degree causing considerable frustration for her. However, to get or not to get a college degree causes ambivalence:

Sometimes I think that maybe I should just do it, it's not hard. It's just useless. But then you get a paper that has your name on it, so it's kind of you know. I thought 'Okay, I'm not going to go to college', I'm going to have more work experience than people that are going to college. So that's a plus. But it's not a plus. Because you know, they still just want you to have a college degree.

Not having the right qualifications has implications for how she searches for a job, and usually she does not apply for jobs that require a degree. However, encouraged by her mother, she actively tries to "get over" herself:

So in the last couple of months, I did try to get over myself in that, to just send it. But I didn't - like - sometimes you don't even get a reply. What am I going to do, cry about it? So, I do kind of try to get over myself in situations like that. But yeah. It feels weird.

Applying for jobs that she is underqualified for, results in even more rejections, sometimes without even getting a reply and that takes its toll on her.

In addition to taking responsibility for her situation herself, she also believes that while being unemployed, the least she can do is improve qualifications, not to waste any time: *"If you don't have a job, at least get some more qualifications, while you're looking for a job."* This may reflect the existing of an enterprise culture constructing the jobseeker as a personal brand, however these understandings are marginal in the qualitative data.

Many of the interview participants seem optimistic about their prospects without being able to explain why this is: Marjan says that he is *"much optimistic about the next two months"* referring to the possibility of new openings. Asked about the reason for his optimism, he answers: *"They are also very surprised, but my optimism .. this is who I am."*

Key takeaways

The data documents a highly diverse group of unemployed making it impossible to stereotypify the unemployed in any meaningful way. A large number of unemployed are struggling with long-term unemployment, and in consequence increased risk of poverty. Many, but not all, within this group are lacking skills demanded by the labour market. With regards to the Hecat platform, a large number of clients in the PES are in need of help, not simply knowing the labour market. A core feature of the tool should thus be to highlight services to improve employability.

Further the platform should take into account the self-reinforcing dynamics related to long-term unemployment. The taken-for-grantedness of the problem of becoming long-term unemployed may result in lacking self-confidence from the perspective of the unemployed, apathy or pessimism from perspective of counsellors and, disregard from the perspective of employers who use long-term unemployment as a first sorting criteria.

The relatively soft activation paradigm is associated with unemployed people being lesser prone to self-blame compared to other OECD countries such as Denmark and the United States.

7 Precarious work

As discussed in section 1.1, Slovenia has witnessed a gradual ‘dualization’ of the labour market, pertinent, segmenting the labour force into privileged ‘insiders’ with stable and permanent employment and generous social coverage and a group of ‘outsiders’ working in temporary and precarious forms of employment without adequate labour law and social protection (Bembič and Stanojević, 2016; Kresal, 2020). A process which is pertinent in, but not reserved to, countries resembling the Continental welfare model (Emmenegger et al., 2012; Palier, 2010). Already in 2001 72.4% of all new jobs were temporary in 2001, equating to 10% of the employment stock (Wright et al., 2003). While several reforms have addressed this issue, with some success (Vodopivec, 2019), it is still a prevalent phenomenon (Bembič and Stanojević, 2016). To Hrženjak ‘labour flexibilisation has not developed in the direction of flexicurity but rather towards the precarisation of work and life’ (Hrženjak, 2017: 222). The flexibilization has been complemented by the rise of a variety of atypical forms of work that may be legal but also are used in cases that do not meet the legal requirements for such work (Pecek and Franca, 2019).

7.1 Temporary employment

In a European perspective, Slovenia ranks among countries with the highest incidence of temporary employment (16.8% for persons aged 20-64) and it has the highest share of temporary employment agency workers (4.9%), although the incidence of part-time work is rather low (9.6%) compared to the EU average (18.7%) (Laporšek, 2020: 35). Even though the economy has slowly recovered after the Financial crisis, ‘almost no new standard employments are available in the general labour market, meaning that employment in non-standard working relationships is not voluntary but forced’ (Bembič and Stanojević, 2016; Hrženjak, 2017: 215). The large majority of advertised vacancies (80%) offer fixed-term contracts, paradoxically, despite such contracts, according to the labour law, are limited to situations with time-limited work such as replacement of absent workers or seasonal work (Bembič and Stanojević, 2016). Also the number of self-employed workers is increasing from (8% in 2014), a form of work that, according to Bembič and Stanojević, is ‘often used as a way of masking dependent employment in an entrepreneurial legal form in order to evade the labour rights associated with a regular employment contract and gain on flexibility.’ (Bembič and Stanojević, 2016: 13).

It is foremost young people who partake in precarious work. The 15 to 24 years old in Slovenia have the highest share of temporary employment (66.6 % in 2012) in EU (Bembič and Stanojević, 2016: 11; O’Reilly et al., 2015). In 2017 it was 26.6% among 25-34 years old compared to only 8.8% of older workers (55 to 64 years old) (Laporšek, 2020: 35). This tendency is also reflected in our qualitative material. Here Jana notes that within the cultural field there is almost only short-term contracts available:

I did work a lot of short-termed jobs because in tourism there is not long-termed jobs, just like 3, 4 or 6 months. The last job I had was for one year. I did do a lot of things that was for culture, sports and tourism.

She reveals that finding employment with a duration of year within this field is very rare. Similarly, Jure has at the age of 26 years not experienced any long-term employments and he is so used to those precarious working conditions that he does not really view them as a big problem:

Jure: When my contract has ended they just prolong it for I don't know, six months, and then again and again. It didn't come to that kind of agreement with an employer. (...) Because they are not violating any rules it's okay for them to do that.

I: Why do you think they are doing that?

Jure: I have no idea. Maybe they just need a worker that will help them with the project they are having or something. I don't know. I really don't know what to say.

Multiple times, Jure has experienced being hired on short-term contracts and to him, this is not a problem because it is legal.

7.2 Student work

A substantial proportion of this employment is student work which contains only minimal labour rights protection (Bembič and Stanojević, 2016: 12). Primarily, the interview participants refer to student work for two reasons; 1) they have prolonged their time to graduate due to student work, 2) they have difficulties finding secure employment due to the excessive use of student work and temporary employments. First, student work takes up a lot of time for the interview participants and it contributes to prolonging studies beyond the standardised time:

I have been studying for much longer than I should've. I should have been able to complete my master's by now. But there was a lot of turbulence in my younger years. I was working in student jobs for three years maybe. Then I came back to finish, basically two years plus the thesis. So yeah, that dragged out a lot.

Student work was one out of multiple factors explaining why he prolonged his studies. In addition to prolonging studies, student work can also lead to temporarily quitting studying and strategically using the student status to access and keep interesting student work:

I quit the bachelor's one and a quarter year in. Then I just worked two years straight, and I had the money and the student status. But then I realized I need something more to achieve, so I went back and did my exams.

He realized the potential vulnerability associated with not getting a degree, so he went back and did his/her examens. However, among the interview participants there are also

cases in which they quit getting a degree altogether and thus more insecurely positioned in the labour market today.

The interview participants have no problems identifying the use of student work as a structural problem, and as something that is also linked to terms within specific industries such as tourism. A problem identified by several of our interview participants is that a lot of companies prefer hiring student workers because it is cheaper:

“In tourism, there's a lot of students work. They get a student for those 3-4 month because there are 4 months when a lot of tourists are here, and then in these months, they take quite some students to work with them. And they pay much less for them then to hire someone like me, that would need to be hired for all year. (...) Like I said before, I think this system needs to change a bit the student work. So that tourism they need to change, because they always take the students, because they are cheaper, they can work all the time, nobody says 'oh they are working at night' because if you are a person that work there for a long time, you can always work at night. They say 8 hours pr. day and that's it. Students can work all day, so they would rather have a student, they pay 5 euro pr. hour. 'Goodbye have a nice day' It's not for me. (...) I think the country does nothing about the system, because there is problem even look at for the last 5 years, there is more and more students that are over 30 and they are still students, and they didn't go to college for five years. They just take a student status for working. And they get more much money than a person that work 5 days pr. week the whole year. That's the problem.”

Student workers are more easily adaptable to seasonal work, so besides getting cheaper work force, employers also avoid dealing with having excessive staff in periods without many tourists visiting. Also, students in general do not have as many (caring) responsibilities and thus have no problem working long hours. As they are paid by the hour, they make an ok salary doing this. In many ways students are less prone to criticize bad working conditions and in that sense they are attractive staff. In the long run, however, it might become an issue, also for the student working hard, as they spend a lot of time either studying or not studying at all. In addition, foreign workers also come to the country to do seasonal work for less pay and this lowers salaries according to Jana: *“Students are more cheaper, like season workers from other countries, are a lot more cheaper. They get up here and they work for less. Nobody would like to pay a real prize for your work.”*

7.3 Externalities of precarization

The precarization among young people has several derived negative consequences. For instance, a study has shown how precarization forces young families to ‘re-traditionalize’ relations to a breadwinner model with either mother or father having to take full responsibility for domestic and care work to let the partner comply with the norms of ‘a self-sufficient, competitive, independent individual who is mobile, flexible, fully available and focussed on paid work and, above all, without caring responsibilities’ (Hrženjak, 2017: 227).

Another derived consequence is how being in temporary workplaces young people in a prolonged state of dependency to their parents. A housing market with relatively high and widespread home ownership combined with limited access to credit for people with fixed term contracts either makes them dependent on family loans or prevents them from moving from their parents (Fialho and Høj, 2020). David who is 27 years and currently unemployed, mean that he is still living at home with his parents and he feels impatient in terms of taking the next step and moving in with his girlfriend:

We get like 400€ for just staying alive when you're searching for a job. Being home, working on the thesis, and getting 400€, was okay. It wasn't that bad. But now I just want to go to the next level. I want to go live with my girlfriend somewhere. I need money to pay for a flat and everything.

Ideas about a decent job is shaped by social and economic circumstances as Jure describes here. He would consider any job that provides him with sufficient money to pay for rent as a good job. Drawing on earlier experiences of unemployment when he used to live at home, he is aware that his ideas about a good job has changes or lowered:

What is a good job for me? At this moment right now, I would say just to be paid. At this time, I would say that. But in long-term, something you are ... something that makes you happy. That is the number one thing. That you love to do whatever you are applying to. The money must be good to make a living from month to month, but so you can also put something away, to save some money. (...) When I first became unemployed, I was just looking for the right job. I didn't have that many problems with money because I was like 21, 22, and I still lived with my parents. And I wasn't concerned about the money so much.

Living at home with parents is quite common among our interview participants and it seems that moving away from home and having financial obligations naturally puts pressure on unemployed people and for many that involves lowering ambitions in terms of what kind of jobs they are looking for.

7.4 The precarization dilemma: inescapable fact, unacceptable work, or pathway towards something better?

Increasingly there are discussions about how unemployed people view job quality – addressing whether they are interested in any type of job to get out of unemployment or whether they have ideas about what kind of job they want to have, i.e., in relation to expectations about working conditions. Various characteristics about the labour market shape their ideas. Vera notes that her long working life will probably include working in all sorts of professions, and she views this in a positive light as it gives her the opportunity to try herself out in a number of ways:

People need more opportunities to try ourselves in different areas. Especially when young, really find what makes us happy, what we love doing. (...). Nowadays a job is not something to have for 30 years. But to have for half a

year or a few months, two years, whatever. But just to be prepared to be every day is different. Like this. To be prepared that nothing is stable.

Milan openly discusses working conditions with potential employers and in addition to his age (60 years), he identifies that this is the main reason why he is not able to find a job:

I think that you have certain rights that you need to learn before you decide if you want to get that job or not. And like I said before, now I ask about my rights and the conditions of labour. Then the tone of voice changes, and I know I'm done.

Milan mentions a number of information about the job at hand that he asks about:

Whether it's fulltime/parttime. Working hours, is it morning/afternoon or late-night shifts. Saturdays or Sundays. Let's say, holidays. Can you take a leave or not? When can you do it? And then salary, of course.

Just bringing up these mundane issues seem to be sufficient reason for Milan not finding a job.

According to several interview participants employers put pressure on wages: "Most the employers, try to put you down. " Erika also notes that you usually start off with a very low wage and work your way up:

Erika: Now it's impossible to influence your salary. You get a basic wage, and then through work you can prove yourself and ask for more.

I: Is that also how it's been in your previous jobs?

Erika: Yes, but these were mostly short-term employments, for a year or slightly more. And then there was no possibility to get a raise. It was not enough, unfortunately not.

Danica has a young daughter so she does not want to work extremely long working hours: *"I will not be 12 hours of not being at home. Working hours is eight hours. And after eight hours, if one should drive in and out for two hours, then it is ten hours or more than that. That is too far away."* Her obligations in terms of taking care of her daughter in this case puts constraints on the type of jobs she is looking for.

According to interview participants many Slovenian workers do not want to work nights and weekends, and hence foreigners get those jobs. Bojana tells a story relating to that issue:

I was talking to a person that is the owner of a very famous restaurant in Slovenia, he said to me 'you know what our problem is?' He has a lot of waiters, and most of them are basically people that are living in Slovenia but they came from other countries before. I mean they are like, probably in Slovenia living since the war, you know where they came from, I don't know, Bosnia, Serbian and stuff. He has a lot of that staff, and he's saying 'You know what the problem is? I can't find people that want to work' but he wants to work, so he works 'I have millions, so I wouldn't need to work, but I'm here

every day'. But what he said, most important thing that I heard, and I feel it's kind of good that people don't want to work this way. People want to have their weekends free; they don't want to work Saturday, Sunday... And he was like 'I'm here every day, people don't want to work in the profession'. And I was like, thinking to myself - I didn't say it, but next time maybe, of course not, I'm happy for the people who don't want to be exploited anymore and work, as I know this is a hard profession, work for 16 hours a day like my friend did when he was working as a chef. Well, his health condition just went down the hill, and he was not happy because it was too stressful, too much, it was 24/7 seven days a week and it's not human. So, what they are expecting because they are making too much money on the expense of people, you know just working until exhausting. And this is not right, so I feel that the people don't want to be exploited like that. They don't like to work in the big shops, big cities centre because they need to work Sunday as well. (...) So, the system is like really not supporting the workers and they are just seeing people as workers, not as people, human beings who need their free time to balance their work life. You need to have both. So, I feel that's the main thing missing.

In the quote he raises many related issues of precarity such as globalisation, and ultimately, he characterises the labour market as inhuman and unhealthy.

Klara has recently landed a job and she describes it as the job of her dreams. Exploring further why this is the case, she explains:

Yes, it's been a wish of mine since I was little. (..) Supply officer in the management of hotels. It's related to my high school and university degree, so it's two-in-one. For eight hours. They're registered as a company that employ disabled people. It's my dream job. It's close to my home. The salary.

The job qualifies as a dream job for Klara, mainly because working hours are normal, commuting is limited, and that the salary is ok. She also underlines that it is rare that people actually find a job within their educational field, and this is also linked to job quality: *“A lot of students don't work in the field that they're educated for. I was lucky to do a lot of things that cover my knowledge, within the scope of my education.”*

Marko is originally from Iran and is learning Slovenian. His work experience in Slovenia mainly consists of short-term and physically demanding about and he remarks that this type of work is deeply discouraging to him if he imagines that he will continue doing this type of work, also in the future: *“For me it was hard, not just physical but also mentally. If you work with something, you are not interested in and you think you don't have a future in that, then it's hard.”* He spends his time as unemployed exploring what he wants to work with in the future and this process is very meaningful to him even though it has not resulted in a feasible career strategy yet:

For now, I have other purpose of life, just starting language courses and try to find more opportunities for finding jobs in Slovenia and this is something that was good discovery - If I learn the language, I get better jobs. I learned from zero and I see in the future, that I will find something good for my future. I don't have a problem with that.

Being unemployed, allows Marko to reflect and embark on transitioning to another professional field and he finds this process very meaningful.

Karmen, too, uses her time as unemployed to deeply think about what kind of a job, she wants. She is relatively picky about what kind of jobs she wants to apply for, and due to having saving, she is not forced into applying for a job she does not really want.

I have experience in administration, and that's primarily what I've been searching for. I'm in a position where I don't have to take any job if I don't like it. You know, it's like I'm an OK financially position. So, I have backups from previous jobs. I just saved. You know, my primary goal is to find something that I enjoy. Not just anything, so I'm quite picky as to where I send my CV.

Having savings or parents that can either house or help financially makes a big difference in terms of how picky unemployed people can allow themselves to be. While there are rules that suggest that companies not obeying labour market laws are black-listed and hence unemployed people do not have to accept jobs from them, according to our interview participants, this rule is not always respected. Poor working conditions are indeed identified by the interview participants.

Key take-aways

Precarization is a challenge to job quality – in particular for young and migrants. It is also what makes people migrate to Austria. And on the other hand, it prevents people from moving.

The Hecat platform should find pathways that lead towards employment with decent working conditions (wage, rights). On the other hand, the phenomenon is so prominent that the platform cannot simply exclude precarious jobs from the equation. Precarious jobs may or may not be a stepping stone towards more sustainable job paths. Hecat platform should take this into account when weighing recommendations.

8 Informality in the labour market

8.1 *The shadow-economy*

The shadow economy is deeply embedded into the Slovenian economy and is one of the most important, yet invisible to the outsider, background institutions shaping social behaviour (Jaklič and Zagoršek, 2009). The role of the shadow-economy and informal labour market has a long history dating back at least to the years of being part of the Austro-Hungarian empire and the so-called ‘hidden valley system’ that was established in the local peasant communities in Slovenia as a grey economy of reciprocity and mutuality to subsidize the capitalist system in the hands of foreigners (Jaklič and Zagoršek, 2009). The informal system somehow survived and evolved in the socialist era. Since products and services ensured by law to employees were insufficient, informal social networks of kinship, carried a large burden when it came to providing social protection and welfare to their members (Kolarič et al., 2011). In this was managers of socialist enterprises were involved in a local shadow economy that also introduced market elements of entrepreneurship and creativity allowing for a high standard of living compared other socialist countries (Jaklič and Zagoršek, 2009).

The estimated size of the shadow economy in Slovenia is not high compared to many other countries. An OECD study estimate it to be around 10.2% compared to 17.5% in Italy and 7.5 in Austria 7.5 (Gyomai and Ven, 2014). Other analyses estimate it even higher to around 20 % of GDP (Nastav & Bojnec, 2007; Medina & Schneider, 2018). Jaklič and Zagoršek (2009) argues that while the shadow economy was beneficial to the transition by allowing workers to earn enough untaxed money to maintain social security and allowing companies to pay low wages and thus maintain competitiveness, it more problematic today, not only because of its size but since it ‘sucks up most of entrepreneurial talent and is focused only on small, local operations’. This toleration of the shadow economy also explains why some of the unemployed registered with the ESS continue to work informally and having two sources of income (Ignjatović et al., 2002).

In the interviews, various types of precarious employments came up as they make a difference in terms of shaping the experience of labour market opportunities. The boundaries between being employed and being unemployed are to some extent eroding as also Demaziere & Delpierre highlight in their review deeming unemployment an: “imperfect category: its boundaries should be considered carefully” (Demazière, 2018). Especially informal work and grey economies play a role here. Milan, 60 years old, is formally unemployed but the corona crisis has affected his wife's workplace considerably and therefore he works unpaid every day for 4-5 hours, constituting a part time position in the grey market:

I wouldn't feel good, being useless at home. So, I help her. But now with the situation with COVID19, it impacted her work, to the extent that it reflected to both our situations. I'm doing my best to support her. Every day I ride my

bike to the office, and I stay 4-5 hours in the office. And then once in a while, depending on the needs, I go and get supplies for what we need. Masks/disinfections/special sheets/gloves, anything that the girls need to be protected in their work.

Following up on the description the interviewer catches the need to ambiguity: “So you are both unemployed, and you work?” and Milan answers “Yes, that is right.” He does not describe any difficulties navigating in the grey domain of the labour market and he also explains that it helps him feel supportive and useful in relation to his wife’s company which has suffered serious setback due to Covid_19. Similarly, Erika, 48 years, also testifies to the eroding boundaries between being employed and unemployed, and she thinks that keeping active means that she does not really feel the potential emotional toll of unemployment:

“with my age you can find satisfaction in different jobs. In any kind of work, you can get satisfied. Because for me now, I am not personally affected, because I am unemployed. I have a lot of work. I get occupied with other things that I do. Because I am a part of a volunteer association, I am quite active.”

In her case, doing volunteer work and keeping active mitigates against some of the potential negative consequences of unemployment on wellbeing.

While Erika worked while being officially unemployed, others among our interview participants now struggled with a CV almost blank despite being an adult, because all work experience prior to now has been off the books. I.e., Bojana has worked as a babysitter for 18 years so officially she has had no employment at all. She started her own company working with healing and teaching yoga, but she struggled getting enough clients and corona ended that adventure:

And now I just said to myself, I'm going to look for a job, I don't like it, I'm not that kind of person. Like working from 8-16, I'm a free spirit, it's not actually for me. And I know that I'm going to be very tired, that fitting in the thing that I love to do with other, you know that energetic healing and yoga stuff.. But I'm still sad for trying it this way, because I don't .. right now I don't see other possibilities. Because then it gives you some kind of security, even though we know in these days, nothing is secure.”

She feels forced to find employment that allows her some sort of security; however, she is deeply reluctant in terms of possessing a regular 9-5 job.

8.2 Kinship, networks and networking

Across the interviews, networking is identified as a key dynamic mediating between job candidates and companies, and it can seem almost impossible to get a job a place where you do not know anybody:

In Slovenia, what is important is to know somebody in a certain company. The majority of decisions are made based on some recommendations. So, it is

very hard to look for a job in a company where nobody has ever seen you, and nobody has recommended you.

Often unemployed people are defined as lacking either education or professional experience, however, Jana points out, that these problem identifications seem meaningless because people often hire somebody they know: *“And then again, they pick someone they know, have grandparents with them. There is a problem with this, no matter education or how much experience you have.”* To her, networking, makes the other demands seem meaningless because in the end what it comes down to, is whether you know somebody who can recommend you. David, is also very critical of what he outright calls corruption:

Still, there's too much corruption in Slovenia. So, the jobs that are supported by the state, paid by the state, the biggest ones, you can probably get a job just by knowing the right people. Or they don't put out the job, you know? They don't put it online or officially, or they put it online and officially but then they take the one they know.

Considering the importance of knowing the right people, Vera has developed a strategy that allow her to get to know the right people by offering her services for free as a “test” so that potential employers based on unpaid workshops will offer her a job. She offers her free services:

To be invited. I would convince them, because it will be for free. Offered for free. And the children are happy with me, satisfied, and their teachers will give me an option, a chance. A test.

The importance of networking remains undisputed among the interview participants. To some people that constitutes an enormous problem and for others, they accept it as part of the dynamics characterizing the Slovenian labour market and “work their way around” it. Offering work without getting economic compensation seems like a viable strategy for the individual but at the same time it reproduces precarity.

Key takeaways

Shadow-economy and kin points to a labour market invisible to official statistics and databases. Work is not recognized, although it plays a significant role in society, and this adds to the blurring of boundaries between employed and unemployed. The Hecat tool should recognize that getting a job is related to networks and kin – those without need more support, some ‘open’ positions are not open in reality, while other positions are never visible.

9 Reflections on the HECAT Platform

In the interviews with unemployed people, we asked them about potential needs that the HECAT platform might fill. Unsurprisingly, the question was rather abstract. However, we have included ideas and reflections on the HECAT platform in the following.

9.1 Avoiding bad employers

A recurring theme among the unemployed people in relation to the HECAT platform was, that it would not suggest employment at bad employers. David describes:

David: Perhaps, that thing that the unemployment office would not refer people to bad employers. That's one.

I: And do you think they do now?

David: Yes, definitely. I've heard that they have some internal list of bad employers, but nobody follows that. They would still refer people to them.

9.2 Displaying diverse employment types

In order to get a better understanding of the jobs offered at various sites, David advocates that the platform shows more possibilities in the same search. This would be facilitated by using "and" rather than "or" as a function in the search engine:

David: And if you could also use an 'and command' or an 'or command'. Maybe an 'and' more so you can search for somewhere in this region and also in this region if you're on the border between them. You would want to see only those jobs, probably if you don't want to drive through the whole - you don't want to look up jobs for the whole state you know. “

I: Yeah, if you could only see where it was relevant and also

David: To see if you could get in, if it's for you. It's customized for your education. Not only if it's a bachelor's or if it's a master's, but also which field.

David does programming and might be interesting to consult in relation to developing the platform.

Due to the activities in the shadow economy, a number of the unemployed persons have much work experience but nothing formal. Hence, the need to be able to see and get in contact with firms that are open to the possibility of taking in people without formal education or work experience is sought for, as described in the following:

Perhaps that would be a portal where you would have a list where you can look for any possible funding for self-employment, or to obtain additional

education, informal education to improve your experience. Not just jobs, but everything. Let's say now, I don't know how this would be helpful, but the initiative for me to decide to get the accountant education, but I doubt this because I'm too old to find employment, so I was thinking to go to accounting firms before I start with this formal education. I would just ask for the post where I could learn more and get the experience. That would be good, if you had the portal, so that companies can register. So that companies can be interested in people without experience, and people know they can go there and get the possibility of work.

The platform should include information not only about jobs, but also internships or other possible ways to get a foot inside the door in a firm.

Also Bojana notes, that the platform could be based more on competences needed to do a particular jobs, and less on formal education. Identifying competences needed would also, possibly, give more relevant information what the job actually involves of tasks. Such information is often not available for jobseekers, Bojana informs:

I really feel that one thing that would be beneficial is to be .. maybe connected with those who are prone on competences, and not so much on education. So that you can join the employers and employees, future employees that basically is searching for someone who has this kind of competences or this kind of experiences over the general education. (...) Nobody prepares you for what you will be doing there. And that's a practical aspect I'm actually missing. So when you are searching for the job, you know 'ohh you need to have computer skills, and this and this and that'. Basically nobody explains that you'll be doing that and that.. Nobody explains what you actually do until you are at the interview, but I want to know that before I actually apply for the job. So it's more clear, that this is a no, this is a yes, this is a possibility. This is the information I would love to have.

Assessing more hands-on knowledge about the job at hand, would make her better capable of deciphering what would be a relevant job for her to apply for, and what would not.

Including ratings of companies

Another idea suggested by an interview participant involves including data that makes it possible for the jobseekers to evaluate the quality of the firm:

I could also be data that is not already in the official statistics. Okay, yes. Perhaps, experiences of people working there. Previously and currently. Or awards for worker-friendly companies. But unfortunately, these awards, can be bought nowadays.

Reflecting on the feasibility of adding reliable data about firms, he immediately thinks of the problem of nepotism and doubts that such measure would be possible to attain.

Another interview person also suggests some sort of a rating system based on how past and current employees rate the firm. That should also provide an incentive to get companies to improve working conditions:

Yeah. Actually, if we take booking. You get the ratings of the guests from the hotel. It's 1 to 5. And you could do the same for companies and firms that are hiring people. People would know what to expect. Because of that, I think other companies would be forced to upgrade their experience, their environment, their payroll or something like that. They would all be forced to go forward in all the areas that they are covering.

Expanding on why such ratings would be interesting, Jure notes that he would appreciate information about how a specific job affect him in the long run, both in terms of mental and physical health:

I think mainly how the specific job is concerned with your mental and physical health. I think that would be one of the most profound things for me to see. If I'm working for 30 years for that specific company, how would that affect me in my mental and physical strength or health. I think that would be nice.

Jure's thoughts reflects the need to consider the job quality, not only in a cross-sectional fashion, but rather incorporating a more longitudinal perspective on the matter.

Key takeaways

Reflections on the HECAT platform includes taking into account the quality of the job and of the company offering a job. This involves both hiding bad employers and providing information about the company based on ratings from past and present employees at the firm. The HECAT platform should also in some way consider activities in the shadow economy, i.e. by making explicit what competencies are needed for a particular job rather than only including information about formal education and formal work experience. Adding information about competencies required for a specific job also makes it easier to know whether the job is of relevance and thus navigate the labour market with more information.

10 The effects of the pandemic

The recent crisis, which is spurred by the Covid-19 pandemic and consequent economic decline (OECD, 2020b), which amounted to 2.3% of GDP in the first quarter of 2020 year on year (Statistični urad Republike Slovenije, 2020) has also affected Slovenian labour market. The causes of economic decline are similar to those in other countries: the quarantine and travel restrictions caused numerous problems on the supply side, while increased uncertainty and supply side problems caused a decline on the demand side (OECD, 2020b). Companies, despite support from the governments, were unable to extend fixed-term contracts, new entrants into the labour market were unable to find jobs, etc. Labour market situation began deteriorating fast. Between December 2019 and June 2020 the number of registered unemployed in Slovenia increased from 75 thousand to 89 thousand, which represents an 18.7% increase, and a sharp turn away from the positive trends, that were recorded in the labour market since 2014.

The increase in the number of unemployed was most pronounced among those, who worked previously in Accommodation and Food Service Activities, Manufacturing, Transportation and storage, and Wholesale and retail trade. The number of unemployed from the Accommodation and Food Service Activities increased by even 66%. The number of unemployed who previously worked in Administrative and support service activities as well as Arts, entertainment and recreation also increased significantly. However, since the beginning of 2021, the number of unemployed has decreased significantly to around 83 thousand in March – a level coming close to the pre-Covid situation. This, however, does not implicate that the labour situation has normalised, since many companies still rely on Covid-19-related state subsidies. One of the more worrying tendencies is the rise in the share of long-term unemployed going from around 43% in 2019 to more than 50% in March 2021. Another is the rising share of young people going from around 9% in 2019 to around 20% in March 2021.

The pandemic has unsurprisingly resulted in increased competition and thus lowered chances of finding a job which is also reflected as an important theme across the interview (interviews were carried out in Summer/Autumn 2020). Here Karmen, 27:

Karmen: I'm quite good at interviews, but because of the virus I ran into some problems. (...) I got into a couple of interviews, but apparently there is much more competition now, because lots of people have lost their jobs. So, I didn't get any jobs.

Jana similarly describes a desert with no new jobs being posted and very little feedback on the few applications she managed to send.

Jana: I think that corona did effect everybody that search for jobs, because everything did stop. Nobody applied for jobs, there is nobody searching for new person working. (..) And there is a lot of things like that, that our factories are taking away people, so they are losing jobs.

While most interview participants recognize difficulties related to corona, some remain optimistic and still believe in the fundamental idea that people who want to find work will be able to despite external factors and insecurity in the labour market. Here is Klara: “People that want to work will find work, regardless of their status. It's my character I am optimistic.” She goes on reflecting about the corona and the doubt it gives rise to:

Klara: A lot of people were let go. I was one of them. Companies have lost a lot, and a lot of people lost their work. I was afraid of how these people would take it and how society can cope.

I: How do you see this now?

Klara: That it will be difficult, and hard. In Slovenia we will have to fight and work hard. I think that it is, and I hope the corona ends.

Acknowledging the hardships caused by corona in the Slovenian labour market, Klara is ready to work hard until the pandemic subsidies.

As already noted above, the job openings on Slovenian labour market are to some degree affected by networking. However, to some reaching out to family and friends for the sake of finding a job is associated with not being able to live up to these norms:

I think I want to prove my own worth. It's not like ‘hey, I'm his nephew’ or something. I think I should just prove my own worth. It's a unique position for me as well, because I never had a problem getting a job. So now I have to kind of re-evaluate what morals I can kind of bend.

The increased competition in the face of the pandemic might enable more informal dynamics as people become extra vulnerable and thus willing to “bend her moral” and she becomes willing to use all possible means:

Usually, I don't really have a problem getting a job. I'm quite good at interviews, but because of the virus I ran into some problems. So, I wasn't even sure if I should go to ask for help, because I usually do very well on my own. So, I was a bit hesitant about that, but when I decided I talked to some friends about how the system worked, because I don't know... I'm not the type of person to ask for help usually.

In addition to challenging the justification of networking in relation to nepotism, going through family and friends to get referrals also collides with self-sufficiency ideals, but these might be increasingly marginalised in the face of the pandemic and its repercussions.

Key takeaways

It is too early to estimate the long-term effect of the Covid-10 pandemic on the labour market, in particular when state subsidy-schemes will be out-phased. However, the pandemic already has some dynamics on the labour market. For instance, it looks like those already located outside of the labour market as well as young people are having a harder

time re-entering. Further, in a situation in which much communication has moved online and employers are more hesitant to hire, the importance of social networks in order to acquire a job may be strengthened, which, again, may explain why long-term unemployed and young people are hit hardest by the pandemic's effects on the labour market.

11 Conclusion

The aim of this deliverable was to describe the ‘user context’ of the Hecat platform underpinned by a ‘sociologically-led user design’ and the ethos of working **with** rather than **on** the unemployed. This entails taking departure in the ‘experience of unemployment’ from the unemployed, and the counsellors working at the ‘street-level’ of public employment services.

In conclusion, we highlight five of the most important findings in relation to developing the HECAT platform.

First, a striking finding distinguishing the Slovenian PES from many other European employment services is that it is best described as a ‘soft’ version of New Public Management. The Slovenian employment system is a hybrid with elements of both classic de-commodifying welfare and workfare elements of both work first and social investment. Due to both the relatively small size of the country and the organization of the PES within one state agency, the governance of the system of Slovenian PES is characterized by a short distance from central to the local level. Although the regional and local employment offices are measured and benchmarked according to performance indicators, the governance, unlike in many other countries, is trust- and dialogue based. Related to this, counsellors enjoy a large amount of **discretion** in their work with unemployed people. We see a strong professional ethos of care and ambition to work *with* the unemployed enabled by a relatively flexible system, and counsellors can work independently using their discretion rather than imposing the same standardized obligations and sanctions on all citizens. Customized individual plans that consider personal, social and economic circumstances are used, but counsellors have a high workload. A majority of the interview participants feel that their needs are met and understood by their counsellors, and a minority expresses that they feel left to themselves.

Secondly, we identify a tension between, on the one hand, policy intentions and, on the other hand, the local reality at PES and the reality of the face-to-face interactions between unemployed and counsellors. Policies and programmes indicate a strong will to **social investment** and increasing the employability of the unemployed by increasing his or her skills and competences while PES in reality has very **scarce resources** for such measures.

Thirdly, the data documents a highly diverse group of unemployed people who have different preferences depending on stages of life, background, etc. However, a large proportion of unemployed are struggling with **long-term unemployment** and the platform should take into account the self-reinforcing dynamics related to long-term unemployment. With regards to the platform, a large number of clients in the PES are in need of help, not simply knowing the labour market. A core feature of the tool should thus be to highlight services to improve employability.

Fourth, an important aspect of the Slovenian labour market is the **shadow economy** as it shapes both the past of current jobseekers as well as it impacts on in their ideas about how to navigate the Slovenian labour market. Further, significant role of the shadow economy is blurring the boundaries between work and unemployment and active and inactive, since many, both officially employed and unemployed, supplement their income through undeclared work. Also, precarious and fixed term contracts play an increasingly important role shaping dynamics on the labour market.

Fifth, exploring the unemployment experience has made visible the many and heterogenous reflections Slovenian jobseekers have on **job quality** in light of both shadow

economy and fixed term contracts and in light of their personal situation and current needs and long-term aspirations. We highlight the need to take such reflections on job quality into consideration when developing the algorithm and its recommendations. The platform should find pathways that lead *towards* employment with decent working conditions (wage, rights, meaningfulness). The phenomenon of the shadow economy and precarity is so prominent that the platform cannot simply exclude precarious jobs from this equation. Precarious jobs may or may not be a steppingstone towards more sustainable job paths. Hecat platform should take this into account when weighing recommendations. Again, taking the large heterogeneity into account seem crucial for developing a helpful tool, supporting the unemployed people in navigating the Slovenian labour market.

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Appendix 1.1.

HECAT Interviewguide for PES counselors

We are working on a research project HECAT dedicated to understanding big data and algorithm usage within Public Employment Services (PES). The primary aims is to work towards developing and piloting an ethical algorithm and platform for use by PES and unemployed people to assist with decision making and distribution of meaningful resources. We aim to develop a tool that will unemployed people and therefore also assist you in your work. Before developing the platform we need to understand the local context better and especially your work with the unemployed. In order to do so, we would like to interview you for approximately 45 minutes duration. Talking to you is necessary for us to be able to develop a platform that is helpful to your citizens. All material will be anonymized. Do you have any questions before we begin?

Introduction

Can you briefly introduce yourself; name, age, nationality, who do you live with and where, number of children, educational background, job in PES, how many years of experience in PES? Other relevant work experience from elsewhere than PES? Have you tried being unemployed yourself?

Nature of the work

- Can you describe the group of unemployed people you work with? (educational level, gender, age)
- What are the conditions for receiving unemployment benefit? Do you find these conditions reasonable?
- What are the typical trajectories of unemployed when entering PES (what services, what benefits, what actions)? Please provide an example.
- How and to what extend are services personalized towards the individual unemployed? Please provide an example.
- What would you say are some of the most meaningful activities you provide?/What are you most proud of in your work with unemployed people?
- What the biggest challenges are in your experience, in working with unemployed people?
- Could you describe a typical day of work?
- How is your workload? How many unemployed people do you follow? Do you have standardized procedures for conversations with the unemployed and if so, what do you think of them?
- How do you assess the job search, and from your perspective what is a good job search?

Assessment and decision-making

- *You use a questionnaire to assess the unemployed people* – What are its main characteristics?

- How do you experience using that “tool” - does it help you customizing the effort toward a particular person?
- When working with a client, try to describe how you reach decisions about what happen? What information (about the unemployed, labour market, rules, etc) do you need to make good decisions? How do you gather this information? How are the needs and wishes of the unemployed included in the decision-making?
- What role does the meetings with unemployed play?
- How much discretion do you have, according to law and rules, in deciding what kind of services that are offered (as well as obligations) to the individual unemployed?
- From your perspective, what competences does a ‘good’ job counselor have? In an ideal world, what information and knowledge would the job counselor be in possession of to do the best counseling?

Documentation and evaluation

- How do you document/register your work?
- How much time do you spend on documentation?
- Do you experience it as meaningful, too little or too much?
- How is your performance as a job counselor evaluated? How is the performance of the local office evaluated? What do these evaluations mean for your work? Do you find them meaningful?
- Since working at PES, have you experienced any changes in the way of assessing performance, and what do you think about it?

Control and sanctions

- Can you describe how you control the unemployed people you follow?
- How often do you employ warnings and sanctions and what is the effect in your experience?
- What do you think about this system of control? Does it make collaborating with the unemployed harder or easier?

Imagine...

- If you were responsible for changing the system; what elements would you keep and perhaps even do more of and what would you change?
- Imagine an intelligent device that could visualize and estimate the likelihood of different future scenarios of your clients’ future professional career – what kind of scenarios would you like to be able to see?
- Imagine an intelligent device that could tell you any detail about the labour market – what kind of information would you like it to provide to you?

If there is more time:

Gradual decrease

What are the unemployed people’s responses to the gradual fall of the unemployment benefits (the benefit is in the amount of 80% of the employment compensation for the first three months, 60% for the next 9 months and 50% thereafter)

Do you ever explain this rule and if so, how?

How do you personally feel about this rule ?

COVID-19 crisis and its effects

How has the crisis affected your everyday practises? How did you work these last 3 months?

Has the COVID-19 brought about any insights into what activities are more valuable and what activities are less valuable?

What do you see as the biggest challenges in the aftermath of the crisis?

Vulnerable groups

Can you tell us about the programs set in place to help particular vulnerable groups? (NEET "Not in Education, Employment, or Training", older unemployed, unemployed for more than 12 months) or older unemployed people? Do they work? Do you any ideas about how to improve them?

I do not have any more questions. Are there any aspects of your work that we have not talked about but that are important to understand your work? Do you have any questions for me before we are done here? Otherwise, thank you so much for your time and contribution to the project.

Appendix 1.2.

HECAT

Interviewguide for unemployed in Slovenia

We are part of a research project HECAT dedicated to understanding big data and algorithm usage within Public Employment Services (PES) which is funded by the European Commission. The primary aim is to work towards developing and piloting an ethical algorithm and platform for use by PES and unemployed people to assist with decision making and distribution of meaningful resources. We aim to develop a tool that will enable PES to work *with* unemployed people not *on* them. Before developing the platform we need to understand the local context, especially the needs of the users, that is the unemployed. In order to do so, we would like to interview you for approximately 45 minutes. When sharing your insights and experiences you contribute developing a tool that is useful and meaningful to the users of PES. All material will be anonymized. Do you have any questions before we begin?

Introduction

- Can you briefly introduce yourself: name, age, nationality, who do you live with and where, number of children, educational and professional background?
- How did you become unemployed? (Also when, and in what circumstances? Did you work before, and if so, what kind of job did you had?)
- When people ask you what you do, what do you answer them?
- What does a typical day look like for you?

Labour market and job search

- What have been the greatest challenges with finding a job? Why do you think have been the main obstacles? What needs to happen or change for you to get a job?
- How do you search for jobs (soliciting the help of friends or relatives; collecting and using job offer ads, exploring internet, contacting PES, etc.), and what is the most suitable for you? Have you been in contact with employers (e.g. internships, job interviews)?
 - o *When you search for jobs, what kind of electronic devices do you normally use? With what type of internet connection?*
 - o *Where (physical space, location) and when do you connect to the internet?*
 - o *What type of user are you in terms of digital knowledge? (advanced, medium, low) Could you explain to us what kind of tools or applications do you normally use?*
- What is a 'good job' for you? Have your expectations changed during your time of being unemployed?
- What have you learned about how the labour market works during your time as unemployed?
- If you think of the decisions you have taken during your time as unemployed, which have you been most in doubt about?

Experiencing PES

- How often have you been in contact with PES (and how)?
- How do you feel before an interview in the employment office? Do you make any preparations?
- How was the first meeting with your counselor? Describe the place it took place. How was the relation between you and the counselor? Did you feel more or less motivated after the meeting?
- How did the counselor come to an understanding of your situation (what questions, role of questionnaire, etc.)?
- How did you decide on future actions and plans? Did/does the plan correspond with/take into account your own wishes and needs?
- Are you obliged to use certain ICT tools, for instance for registering activities?
- What do you think about the obligations that PES require you to live up to? Are they meaningful, realistic, just? Have you thought about the possibility of you getting sanctioned for not complying with the obligations?
- What does it take for you to feel that PES/counselor is working together *with* and not *on* you? Have you experienced working *with* and/or *on* you?
- If you were responsible for changing the system; what elements would you keep and perhaps even do more of and what would you change?

Profiling and artificial intelligence

- Imagine an intelligent device that could visualize and estimate the likelihood of different future scenarios of your future professional career – what kind of scenarios would you like to be able to see? Imagine that someone could tell and show you exactly how possibly different career path would be for you – what would you like to know more about?
- Imagine an intelligent device that could tell you any detail about the labour market – what kind of information would you like it to give you?

I do not have any more questions. Are there any aspects that we have not talked about but you find important? Do you have any questions for me before we are done here? Otherwise, thank you so much for your time and contribution to the project.

Appendix 1.3.

HECAT Interviewguide for Focus groups with PES counselors

We are working on a research project HECAT dedicated to understanding big data and algorithm usage within Public Employment Services (PES). The primary aim is to work towards developing and piloting an ethical algorithm and platform for use by PES and unemployed people to assist with decision making and distribution of meaningful resources. We aim to develop a tool that will help unemployed people and therefore also assist you in your work. Before developing the platform we need to understand the local context better and especially your work with the unemployed. All material will be anonymized. Do you have any questions before we begin?

Job search and labour market

- Can you briefly describe the groups of unemployed people you work with?
- What are the most common explanations for why your clients have become unemployed?
- What are the biggest barriers on the labour market that prevents your clients from getting a job?
- What are the reasons when your clients manage to get a job?
- What are the quality of the jobs they acquire? **What is a decent job?**
 - o Temporary/permanent positions
 - o Wages, pension, etc.
 - o Do the jobs fit their competences or are they over- or underqualified?
 - o Are they able to stay on the labour market or do you typically see them again later?
- How do you see the labour market – what makes people change jobs? How do they advance in their careers?
- How do you assess the job search, and from your perspective what is a good job search?
- In an ideal world how would your role be in the matching of client and employer?

Assessment and decision-making

- When working with a client, try to describe how you reach decisions about what happens? What information (about the unemployed, labour market, rules, etc) do you need to make good decisions? How do you gather this information? How are the needs and wishes of the unemployed included in the decision-making?
 - o Ask about KIK
- What role does the *meetings* with unemployed play?

Imagine...

- If you were responsible for changing the system; what elements would you keep and perhaps even do more of and what would you change?
- Imagine an intelligent device that could visualize and estimate the likelihood of different future scenarios of your clients' future professional career – what kind of scenarios would you like to be able to see?

- Imagine an intelligent device that could tell you any detail about the labour market – what kind of information would you like it to provide to you?

We do not have any more questions. Are there any aspects of your work that we have not talked about but that are important to understand your work? Do you have any questions for me before we are done here? Otherwise, thank you so much for your time and contribution to the project.